

The Cluster Luminosity Function

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Abstract

This study of the cluster luminosity function is based on photometric data of 80 rich northern Abell clusters. The data was obtained by scanning red Palomar Sky Survey plates. Magnitudes were calibrated using CCD imaging. All clusters have redshifts $z < 0.1$.

To all individual cluster luminosity function a Schechter function was fitted. The variance in Schechter parameters M^* and α was larger than could be expected if one assumes all luminosity functions are drawn from a universal Schechter luminosity function.

Most important results however were obtained by combining data of several clusters into composite luminosity functions. We divided the total sample in three subsamples of increasing cluster richness. This brought to light that the richer the cluster the brighter M^* is. So apparently very rich clusters have relatively more bright galaxies. Another, but less well established feature is that poor clusters seem to have a steeper faint-end slope α .

Of all composite luminosity functions the Bautz-Morgan $> II$ sample luminosity function resembles most the Schechter function. Next best is the luminosity function of poor clusters and clusters with $\sigma_v < 800 km/s$.

An important discovery is that the luminosity function of the center of the cluster is different from the outside luminosity function. Surprisingly the difference in distribution occurs up to a relatively faint magnitude of $M_R \sim -22$ ($H_0 = 50 km/s/Mpc$) which is $\sim 0.5 mag$ fainter than M^* . This might be the first evidence for luminosity segregation in clusters.

Our results indicate that the cluster LF is effected by dynamical processes in clusters, such as merging and tidal interactions.

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Chapter 1

Introduction

This graduation paper is the result of a study of the cluster luminosity function based on photometric data of more than 80 Abell clusters. The study was done by the author under supervision of Dr. Peter Katgert.

The galaxy luminosity function gives the distribution of galaxy luminosities. In this paper the object of study is the general LF, i.e. the luminosity distribution summed over all galaxy types. The distribution of luminosities of one type of galaxy is called a specific LF. A review of both kind of LFs is the article of Binggeli, Sandage & Tammann (1988).

Since the 1970's it has been clear that the LF of galaxies outside clusters (the field LF) is different from the LF of cluster galaxies.

But there are many similarities between cluster and field LF. Both have a power law distribution at faint magnitudes (say $M_R < -22$ for $H_0 = 50 \text{ km/s/Mpc}$) with a rather steep fall-off at brighter magnitude. The magnitude where the power law behaviour changes into a more or less exponential fall-off is usually denoted by M^* .

The general form of the galaxy LF is approximated by the much used Schechter (1976) function:

$$n(L) dL = n^* \exp\left(-\frac{L}{L^*}\right) \left(\frac{L}{L^*}\right)^\alpha d\frac{L}{L^*} \quad (1.1)$$

where $n(L)$ is the number of galaxies within a luminosity range $(L, L + dL)$, L^* is related to the characteristic magnitude M^* and α gives the slope of the power law at faint luminosities. n^* is a normalization factor. Note that for $\alpha < -1$ the total number of galaxies (integration of $n(L)$ to $L = 0$) is infinite.

The overall form of the LF may offer some clues to the galaxy formation process. An attempt to explain the form of the LF is the Press & Schechter (1974) theory. Press & Schechter derived a mass function, assuming Gaussian fluctuation of the density field. This mass function also has a power law behaviour with a cut-off at some characteristic mass. The size of the

characteristic mass is related to the amplitude of the density field at a certain redshift.

However the Press & Schechter theory has some inconsistencies. Some of which were solved by Bond *et al.* (1991). Another problem is the relation between the cosmological mass function (which includes other objects like clusters) and the galaxy LF. This involves a very uncertain relation between galaxy mass including the halo and the galaxy luminosity. The problem is discussed in a paper by Peacock & Heavens (1990), who also offer a possible solution.

The best established LF is the field LF (e.g. see Efstathiou *et al.* (1988) and Loveday *et al.* (1992)). The form of it is very well described by equation 1.1, with $\alpha = -1.0$. For the field LF the normalization factor n^* (also denoted ϕ^*) gives the galaxy density per unit volume per unit luminosity (Loveday *et al.* found $\phi^* = 1.2 \times 10^{-2} Mpc^{-3}$ for $H_0 = 100 km s^{-1} Mpc^{-1}$).

Less well established is the cluster LF. The question is if there are variations in cluster LF, or to put it another way: is there a universal cluster LF? Studying the LF of clusters is important, because the LF is likely to have changed from its initial form due to galaxy-galaxy interactions and other dynamical processes.

An important feature of some clusters is the presence of a huge elliptical galaxy in the center, a cD or D galaxy. Often such a galaxy has an extended halo of stars around it. The origin of cD galaxies is uncertain. According to one scenario (see Hausman & Ostriker, 1978 and Malamuth & Richstone, 1984) a cD galaxy is the product of merger processes in cores of clusters. A cD galaxy then grows by swallowing other galaxies, hence the name "cannibalism". Evidence for this theory is the multiple cores sometimes found in cD galaxies.

Another theory is that cD galaxies originated in smaller groups of galaxies, which at a later era ended up in clusters (cD galaxies are also found in groups of galaxies).

According to Merritt (1984) merging of galaxies in clusters is unlikely. The most important process affecting the cluster LF is stripping of stars from galaxies due to the tidal field of the cluster potential. Stripping is most important at the time of cluster collapse. The radius of a galaxy is limited by the cluster tidal field. Only a galaxy at the center of the potential is not affected by this tidal interaction. So a central galaxy can collect all the debris formed by the tidal stripping of galaxies in the core. An argument for this theory is that the diffuse light found in clusters without cDs has the same density distribution as haloes of cD galaxies. In other words this diffuse light is just a cD halo without the cD galaxy.

According to both theories the cluster LF is expected to be the result of a galaxy formation process plus a later evolution due to various dynamical processes. Merging is one of those possible processes. Merging is the process that, as the result of a collision, two galaxies form a new, more massive, galaxy. For merging to occur the galaxy density should be high, but the approach velocity of the two galaxies should not be too high. Otherwise only collisional stripping occurs. The interaction then results in the removal of loosely bound stars. Other stripping processes are the already mentioned tidal stripping of stars and ram pressure stripping. The latter process removes gas from galaxies, due to interaction with the cluster medium.

Stripping of stars mostly depend on galaxy density. So if all these dynamical processes are important one expects that the cluster LF depends on galaxy density, hence on cluster richness. Velocity dispersion also plays a role. An high cluster velocity dispersion may suppress galaxy merging.

A dynamical process not yet mentioned is dynamical friction. Dynamical friction is the process that more massive objects loose kinetic energy to their environment. This process is a manifestation of two-body relaxation. Note that the gravitational field of the cluster as an whole has the same effect on all galaxies, whereas two body relaxation processes tend to slow down more massive galaxies. Two body relaxation is more effective if more cluster mass is (initially) associated with the galaxies. The slowing down may effect that more massive galaxies end up in the center of the cluster. This is called luminosity segregation i.e. the LF of galaxies in the center of clusters should contain more bright galaxies. For a discussion see Merritt (1984 & 1985).

A final word has to be said about the classification of clusters. In this study we will use the Bautz-Morgan (BM) classification, which is based on the presence of a dominating galaxy. BM I clusters contain one very bright galaxy, often a cD galaxy. The magnitude difference between first and second ranked galaxy is rather large in such a cluster. BM II have two dominating galaxies or a less dominating first ranked galaxy. Finally, BM III clusters have no dominating galaxy.

This paper will provide evidence that the LF of clusters depends on cluster properties related to the various dynamical processes. The evidence is based on the largest sample ever used to study the cluster LF.

Throughout this paper an Hubble constant $H_0 = 50 \text{ km/s/Mpc}$ is used.

Chapter 2

Data and Reductions

2.1 The Sample

The 80 clusters of this study come from a sample Rhee, van Haarlem & Katgert (1991) used for studying the elongation of Abell clusters. All clusters lie in a cone centered on the north galactic pole given by: $10^h \leq \alpha \leq 18^h$, $b \geq 30^\circ$, $\delta \geq -25^\circ$. The clusters have richness class ≥ 1 and redshift ≤ 0.1 .

The data were obtained by scanning red Palomar Sky Survey plates with the Leiden Astroscaan automatic plate measuring machine. Magnitudes were calibrated using CCD-imaging with a KPNO-R filter. The observations were made with the 1.0m Kapteyn Telescope at La Palma in April 1988.

In this study we limit ourselves to the galaxies within a circular area of $2Mpc$ from the cluster center. For a number of clusters the area scanned was not large enough to include $2Mpc$ from the cluster center. In that case we adopted a smaller radius, unless a radius of $1.5Mpc$ was still too large to cover the scanned area, then we left the cluster out of our sample. (The original sample consisted of 92 clusters.)

We did not adopt a uniform absolute magnitude limit for all cluster luminosity functions. The reason is that our redshift range is rather large and this, combined with the different plate qualities and cluster richness values, makes it impossible to define a good overall magnitude limit unless it be fairly bright. The apparent magnitude limits adapted by us are in the range $16.4 \leq m_R \leq 18.3$, in absolute magnitudes the range is $-21.7 \leq M_R \leq -18.7$.

One of the problems with a large sample like this is that not for all clusters reliable redshifts are known. We made use of the compilation from Strubble & Rood (1991). Many adopted redshifts are based on only one redshift measurement ($N_z = 1$ see column 3 in table B.1). It is not unlikely that in such a case a non-cluster member was measured. We investigated that possibility by making use of the m_{10} distance relation. We will illustrate this in section 2.9. For the moment it suffices to mention that we left some clusters out of our original sample, because we have enough reason to believe that the currently adopted cluster redshifts are unreliable.

Figure 2.1: Redshift distribution of the sample.

The final sample of 80 clusters spans a wide range of morphological types. Thus forming a large and statistically significant data set for studying the luminosity function (LF) of galaxies. The sample and relevant data are listed in table B.1.

Figure 2.1 shows the distribution of cluster redshifts of the final sample. The fact that the redshift distribution is rising up to a redshift $z \sim 0.08$ indicates the sample is rather representative until that magnitude.

2.2 Reduction of the Digitized Images.¹

In order to arrive at an objective method for finding cluster galaxies and their positions we decided to scan Palomar Sky Survey plates using the Leiden Astroscan automatic plate measuring machine. We shall first describe the scanning method and the three stages one must go through to reduce the digitized image to a list of candidate galaxies.

The Leiden plate measuring machine is a computer controlled micro-densitometer capable of producing a two dimensional digital photographic density map from a photographic plate. The machine has been described by Swaans (1981).

The fields to be scanned are subdivided into 1024 pixel arrays. We work with a $20\mu m$ square aperture, (i.e. averaging the read-out of four $10\mu m \times 10\mu m$ pixels), in which case 1024 pixels correspond to a linear dimension of $2.048cm$ or $23.1arc\ minutes$ on the Palomar Sky Survey plate-scale. The offline reduction is then done for each 1024 array individually.

The background detection proceeds as follows. We define the background as containing only photographic density fluctuations with spatial frequencies lower than a selected cut-off

¹Taken from George Rhee, 1989, Ph.D. Thesis, chapter 8, section 2.2.

frequency. The initial array of data is divided into small equal square submatrices with sizes corresponding to this cut-off frequency. A histogram of the photographic densities in each submatrix is then computed. The low density wing of the histogram is used to fit a gaussian as a model of the background.

Objects are detected by defining a threshold level on the background subtracted matrix. The matrix is then clipped at a threshold level, defined in terms of the noise (in photographic density) in the background averaged over the whole matrix. Each group of one or more adjacent pixels with densities above the threshold level is considered to be a separate object.

The 3σ level is defined as the plate limit. Several parameters are stored for each object. The two parameters important for the present study are object position and the object brightness. The object brightness is defined as the sum of the object intensities (derived from the photographic densities using an assumed characteristic curve) above the 3σ level.

Using the density matrix of an object we calculate its size and the first moment of the object image.

A diagram is then plotted of the size parameter versus object magnitude, the object brightness defined above. It is this diagram which we use to discriminate between stars and galaxies. Using 40 objects (20 stars and 20 galaxies) classified by eye the position of a line separating stars from non-stellars (assumed to be all galaxies) is determined. All objects above this line (i.e. with $1/r$ larger than the minimum value for its brightness) are defined as no-stellars, i.e. galaxies.

2.3 Photometric Calibration

Magnitudes were calibrated using CCD frames obtained with the 1.0m Kapteyn Telescope at La Palma. Images were made with a KPNO-R filter. A GEC chip (number 3) was used at the f/15 focus. The field of view of the chip is 1.9 by 2.9 *arcmin* and the pixel size is 0.30 *arcsec*. The observations were made during the nights of 9 to 15 April 1988 by Peter Katgert and Michiel van Haarlem. The integration time per frame was 120s. On average four CCD frames per cluster were used. Between cluster observations two equatorial stars from Landolt (1983) were observed (about 26 stars per night). The standard deviation in the photometric constants over the set of standards stars is ~ 0.03 magnitudes.

For the reduction the FIGARO and DAOPHOT packages were used. Bias and dark current frames were subtracted from the image, which then was flat fielded. The next step was deriving total magnitudes for the galaxies in each field by means of aperture photometry.

On average nine galaxies per cluster were used to make a calibration from an Astroscan magnitude derived from the object plate densities, m_{asc} , to m_R . We assumed a linear relation between m_{asc} and m_R with the slope being the same for all fields, but zero-points variations from field to field.

The fitting was done as follows. All Astroscan and CCD magnitudes were put together and a least square fit of Astroscan to CCD magnitudes was made. The slope found this way was then

Figure 2.2: Astroscan versus CCD magnitudes, uncorrected (left) and corrected for different zero-points.

used to make least square fits to find the zero-points of the different fields. Then the zero-points were subtracted from the Astroscan magnitudes. The whole process was then repeated several times with the “corrected magnitudes”, instead of the original obtained Astroscan magnitudes. This was done until a stable value for the overall slope was found. The relation found was: $m_R = 0.885m_{asc} + zeropoint$. The dispersion in the final relation is 0.172 CCD magnitudes. Note that this relation is based on the total sample of 92 clusters.

Having found an overall slope, a least square fit was made to the individual fields to estimate the actual zero-points of each field. On average the dispersion in the magnitudes per cluster is 0.176 CCD magnitudes (fitting the zero-point introduces an extra degree of freedom, hence the slightly larger value for the dispersion).

During our study it appeared something was wrong with the photometry of the Coma cluster (A1656). Indications were: the best fitting Schechter M^* was too faint, the brightest galaxies having $M_R > -23.5$. Comparing the LF of Coma with the LF Lugger (1986) obtained for Coma, confirmed our suspicions. Further evidence was found in the fact that Schechter’s normalization factor n^* was much larger than the richness value we obtained (see section 2.8 and chapter 3). However the fit between Astroscan and CCD magnitudes did not show any anomaly. This is an indication that the error is a zero-point error.

To correct for the error we used photometric data of Coma gathered by Mazure *et al.* (1987). Cross-identifying galaxies in their list with our data we obtained red magnitudes (using $b-(b-r)$ magnitudes). Using these magnitudes we determined a new zero-point magnitude for Coma. The new magnitudes are 0.7mag brighter than the ones earlier obtained.

2.4 Definition of the Cluster Center.

We adopted the following method for defining the center of a cluster. We initially took the center of the scanned region as the center of the cluster. Then we corrected the position of the center by adopting the arithmetic mean of the positions of the 50 brightest galaxies within a radius of $1.0Mpc$ from the initial center as a new center. We repeated the process until the last correction was smaller than $0.01Mpc$.

This radius of $1.0Mpc$ was chosen as a compromise between a radius small enough to be unaffected by the borders of the scanned region and large enough to produce a significant arithmetic mean.

Having adopted a cluster center, we calculated the maximum circular area that fits the scanned region. We excluded clusters from our final sample for which this radius is less than $1.5Mpc$.² As a maximum radius we adapted $2.0Mpc$. This was done to treat the sample as uniform as possible.

For 70 of the 80 clusters the region scanned with the Astroscan was large enough to be complete within $2Mpc$ from the center.

2.5 Statistical Corrections for Non-Cluster Members

Most authors (e.g. Dressler, 1978, Lugger, 1986 and Oegerle & Hoessel) correct for field galaxies by using the field number counts of Oemler (1974). His data suggests a power law with a slope of 0.6. However Oemler's data consisted of a hybrid of magnitudes in different passbands, which were converted to passband B_J .

Therefore we made use of the more recent galaxy counts by Metcalfe *et al.* (1991) (UKSTU counts in their figure 8). A least square fit to their data gives the following relation:

$$\log n_f(m_R) = 0.55m_R - 7.45, \quad 15.42 \leq m_R \leq 17.92 \quad (2.1)$$

with n_f being the number of galaxies per square degree per magnitude interval. The slope of 0.55 is not much different from the value Oemler found. Dressler (1978) found a standard deviation of 25% from field to field, using the Shane-Wirtanen counts.

2.6 Other Corrections Applied to the Data

To convert apparent magnitudes to absolute magnitudes a K_z and a galactic absorption correction has to be applied to the data. This was done using the relation $M_R = m_R - \mu - A_R - K_z$, where M_R is the absolute red magnitude, m the apparent magnitude, μ the distance modulus, A_R the galactic absorption and K_z the K-correction, which corrects for the reddening of the spectrum.

²For this reason we left A1185, A1291, A1837 and A2063 out of our original sample.

Figure 2.3: Field galaxy counts (from Metcalfe *et al.*, 1991) with a least square fit (solid line).

The distance modulus was taken to be $\mu = 5 \log(cz/H_0) = 40.879 + 5 \log z$. This formula assumes $q_0 = +1$, q_0 corrections are however not very important for $z < 0.1$ and the q_0 range of interest.

The corrections for galactic absorption and the K-correction were taken from Sandage (1973): $A_R = 0.07(\csc |b| - 1)$ for $|b| < 50^\circ$ and $A_R = 0$ otherwise. The K correction in R is given by $K_z = -2.5 \log(1 + z)$ for $z < 0.1$. Both corrections are small for $z < 0.1$ ($\sim 0.1\text{mag}$).

2.7 Limiting Magnitudes

As Lugger (1986) pointed out, it is important to study luminosity functions by means of a homogeneous sample. Therefore she adapted a uniform absolute magnitude limit of $M_R = -19.8$. However all these clusters have $z \leq 0.037$. In the sample used for this study $z \leq 0.1$. This means that for some clusters the field contamination sets in at brighter absolute magnitude. This has severe consequences for the statistical significance of counts at fainter apparent magnitudes. These counts may be heavily contaminated by field galaxies. The poorest clusters and clusters at high redshifts are most affected by this problem. Furthermore different plate qualities also effect the apparent magnitude limit. For these reasons it was impossible to choose one uniform limiting absolute magnitude for the total sample or it had to be a rather bright one ($\sim -21.5\text{mag}$).

The magnitude limits used in this study were fixed considering the following two aspects:

- What is the contribution of the field galaxies to the total amount of galaxies at a certain magnitude?
- Are there some doubts about completeness at the faint end?

The first point made us define the magnitude limit by demanding the last bin not to be dominated by non-cluster members. In differential form:

$$n_{field}(m_{lim}) = \frac{1}{2}n_{tot}(m_{lim}) \quad (2.2)$$

where $n_{tot}(m)$ denotes the galaxy counts uncorrected for field contamination, m_{lim} is in fact the brightest magnitude $m > 16$ which satisfies (2.2).

Rather than binning the data, we calculated the magnitude limits automatically by smoothing the uncorrected (=cluster + field) magnitude distribution of each cluster and estimating the field contribution using the field number counts mentioned above. The smoothed luminosity distribution was given by:

$$n(m) = \sum_{i=1}^N f(m - m_i) \quad (2.3)$$

where $f(x)$ is a truncated parabola with total width 1, axis x and integrated surface 1, the index numbers all magnitudes. N is the number of galaxies in the magnitude list. Smoothing data this way has the advantage that there is no problem with binning-noise and the magnitude limit can be determined more precise. The smoothed distribution is continuous if the magnitudes are closely spaced. $n(m) > 0$ in the magnitude range we were interested in (roughly $16 < m < 18.5$). After automatic determination of the magnitude limit we critically checked the result by eye. We corrected the magnitude limit in case:

- (a) $n_f(m_{lim})/n_{tot} < 0.5$, but this ratio was more or less constant over a large range and was not much smaller than 0.5 (e.g. A2197).
- (b) $n_f(m_{lim})/n_{tot} > 0.5$, but n_{tot} bends downwards at a brighter magnitude (this can hardly be real, since the number of field galaxies increases for fainter magnitudes). In that case we suspected incompleteness.

These corrections by eye can best be explained using examples. Figures 2.4 and 2.5 show three examples. The solid line depicts half the total number of galaxies (smoothed), the broken line is the expected field contribution. Where the solid line crosses the broken line our criterion for m_{lim} is fulfilled. In case of A978 we adapted the automatically calculated magnitude limit using (2.2), in this case $m_{lim} = 17.44$. A2197 is a fine example of case (a): according to (2.2) $m_{lim} = 16.36$, we set it to $m_{lim} = 17.7$. The third example shows case (b). We were more conservative than our first criterion requires. For A2250 the magnitude limit should, according to (2.2), be $m_{lim} = 18.32$, we adopted $m_{lim} = 18.0$.

We must point out that our criterion can result in some selection effects. A criterion like this can bias towards a steeper faint-end of the luminosity functions for poor clusters.

2.8 A New Cluster Richness Definition

What is meant with "cluster richness" is intuitively clear. In practice however there are some problems when defining cluster richness. Abell's criterion (the number of cluster galaxies within

Figure 2.4: Smoothed luminosity function of A978. Shown are $n_{tot}(m)$ (dotted), half this number (solid) and the expected field contribution (broken line).

Figure 2.5: On the left the smoothed luminosity function of A2197 (no corrections for field galaxies), on the right the uncorrected LF of A2250. Shown are $n_{tot}(m)$ (dotted), half this number (solid) and the expected field contribution (broken line). See text for an explanation about the magnitude limits.

Figure 2.6: Distribution of the apparent (left) and absolute magnitude limits.

a magnitude range m_3 to $m_3 + 2$ within a radius of $1.72z^{-1} \text{ arcmin}$) suffers from the fact that it is based on the magnitude of the third brightest galaxy, which is itself richness dependent.

Since for our sample all redshifts are known we can base a redshift definition on absolute, rather than apparent, magnitude. Furthermore we wanted to avoid a richness definition based on that part of the LF that shows too much variation: the bright end. Given these considerations we defined cluster richness (denoted by RN) as the number of galaxies in magnitude interval $-22.5 \leq M_R \leq -21.5$, within a radius of $2Mpc$ from the clusters center. This number was corrected for expected field contamination. For the 10 clusters that were not complete out to radius of $2Mpc$ we applied a small correction (well within a Poisson error), based on the average cluster profile in our sample.

Figure 2.7 shows the richness distribution according to the above definition.

2.9 Checking the Cluster Distance

Since not all cluster redshift are equally well determined (a number of cluster redshifts are based on just one redshift measurement), we checked the redshift using the tenth ranked galaxy as a distance indicator.

Figure 2.8 shows the relation between $M - m$, as determined from the redshifts, and m_{10} . Clusters with m_{10} fainter than the bulk of magnitudes and with less than 3 redshifts measured were removed from our sample. Those clusters are A924, A991, A1828 and A2168.

It is not necessarily so that the measured redshifts of those clusters are wrong, another possibility is that those clusters are extremely poor (this seems indeed the case with A924 and A991), which is also a good reason to exclude them from our sample.

Figure 2.7: Distribution of cluster richnesses.

Figure 2.8: The apparent magnitude of the tenth ranked cluster as a function of $m - M$. The clusters belonging to the four outliers above the bulk of points were removed from the sample.

Chapter 3

Fits to 80 Cluster Luminosity Functions

3.1 LFs of 80 Cluster

One of the major issues considering cluster LFs is, whether there exists a universal cluster LF. Looking for variations in cluster LFs it is useful to compare the parameters obtained by fitting the Schechter function to the LFs. This way the Schechter parameter M^* may reveal variations in the cut-off magnitude of LFs and variations in α may provide information about the faint-end of the LFs.

A related issue is how well cluster LFs are described by the Schechter function.

For this reason all 80 cluster LFs were fitted to the Schechter function using the Maximum Likelihood technique. This technique states that the best fitting parameters maximize the so-called likelihood function, $\ln \mathcal{L}$, where \mathcal{L} in case of a Schechter distribution function is:

$$\mathcal{L} = \prod_{i=1}^N \frac{n(L_i)}{\int_{L_{lim}}^{\infty} n(L) dL} \quad (3.1)$$

$n(L)$ here refers to the Schechter function (see equation 1.1). The parameter n^* from the Schechter function is fitted by normalizing the Schechter function to the total number of cluster galaxies. The second order derivatives of equation 3.1 (the so called Fisher information) give estimations of the variance in L^* and α and the covariance between those two parameters.

In Appendix A the complete solutions to the likelihood equations are given. Also explained there is how one can easily correct statistically for background contamination using an extension of the Schechter & Press (1976) method and equation 2.1.

The maximum likelihood technique has the advantage over the much used χ^2 method, that the data does not have to be binned. Thus avoiding problems at the bright-end of the LF, where the statistics are usually poor (less than 5 counts per bin).

The maximum likelihood technique was also adopted by Oegerle *et al.* (1986,1987 & 1989) and Lugger (1986), who uses both the χ^2 technique and the maximum likelihood method described by Schechter & Press (1976). However Lugger uses the Schechter & Press method only to fit M^* for a fixed value of α (namely $\alpha = -1.25$).

Comparing the results Lugger obtained using both techniques, reveals that the χ^2 technique results in a brighter fit for M^* , keeping $\alpha = -1.25$

3.2 Statistical Fluctuations of M^* and α Expected in a Schechter Distribution

Following Dressler (1978) we wanted to see what variations to expect in M^* and α on basis of only purely statistical variations. We did this by generating a number of luminosity functions drawn from a Schechter function with $\alpha = -1.25$. These Monte Carlo LFs were fitted using the maximum likelihood method, thus providing a test for this technique.

To draw the LFs we used the method described by Dressler (1978). The computer provides N random numbers between 0 and 1. For a given luminosity limit L_{lim} a random number r corresponds to a luminosity L :

$$r = \int_L^\infty n(L')dL' / \int_{L_{lim}}^\infty n(L')dL' \quad (3.2)$$

where $n(L)$ is the Schechter function.

To see what the influence was of the number of galaxies and the faintness limit M_{lim} on the variance of parameters, we varied the number of magnitudes and M_{lim} systematically.

If the number of magnitudes was small there was a chance that the LF could not be fitted. This is a problem we also had when fitting real data. But in the latter case we could by hand alter the first approximations for M^* and α and then try again. This could not be done in an automatic way when dealing with a large number of Monte Carlo data.

The results of our Monte Carlo scheme are listed in table 3.2. Column (1) gives the number of "galaxies", column (2) the magnitude limit, column (3),(4) and (5) the standard deviation respectively observed correlation in the fitted parameters, column (6) the standard deviation in the fitted M^* with α kept at a value of -1.25 , column (7),(8) and (9) show the variance and covariance in the parameters as estimated by the maximum likelihood method. Column (10) gives the number of Monte Carlo LFs and column (11) shows the number of LFs that could not be fitted automatically.

Figure C.10 (appendix C) pictures the results.

The conclusion confirm Dressler's results, but in addition we have now also information about the expected variance in α . In short: the uncertainty in M^* is not very dependent on M_{lim} and varies with $1/\sqrt{N}$ (which is also predicted by the Fisher information, see appendix A). The uncertainty in α also varies with $1/\sqrt{N}$, but is strongly dependent on the magnitude

limit, as can be expected. The correlation between α and M^* is very strong (~ 0.8). This indicates there is a certain freedom to change α in order to get a better fit at the bright-end. Keeping M^* fixed and making α steeper makes the Schechter distribution to predict more galaxies at the bright-end. This freedom is less if the magnitude limit is faint. This can be seen by looking at the estimated correlations between α and M^* (column (9) of the table), which is lower for fainter magnitude limits.

It appears that the Fisher information gives good estimations of the variance and covariance of the parameters. It slightly overestimates the fit uncertainties. However one must keep in mind that the Fisher informations gives the freedom of fit for the individual fits, whereas the standard deviations give information about uncertainties in the fits *plus* statistical variations in the individual LFs.

Furthermore the Fisher information does not say anything about goodness of fits: it only gives a good estimation, provided that the LF is a Schechter function. However that was the purpose of these tests, namely providing us information about the variance in LFs under the assumption they are drawn from one distribution, the Schechter function.

So on basis of these tests we should not be surprised to see variations in M^* of order $\sim 0.6mag$ and variations in α of order 0.25. Let alone the uncertainty in measured redshifts for some of our clusters! Keeping $\alpha = -1.25$ and fitting only M^* reduces the uncertainty in this parameter by a factor 2.

3.3 Fits to the Schechter Function

The large correlation between M^* and α makes it very difficult to look for intrinsic variations among cluster LFs. For this reason it is very convenient to have α fixed at one value ($\alpha = -1.25$). On the other hand fitting α as well does give information about the faint- end. Fitting only M^* is called a two parameter fit and fitting M^* together with α is called a three parameter fit, because n^* is estimated as well, by normalizing the Schechter function to the number of galaxies. Following Luger (1986) we indicate this by a bracketed number after M^* (e.g. $M^*(2)$ is the value for M^* if $\alpha = -1.25$).

The fitted Schechter parameters are found in tables B.2 & B.3 in Appendix B. Table B.2 list the results if the brightest cluster members are included. Table B.3 list the same parameters, but now the fits were made with the first ranked galaxy *within a radius of 0.6Mpc from the cluster center* excluded. We used this procedure to increase the chance to exclude the brightest cluster member (BCM) and not a bright galaxy in the fore-ground, which is corrected for statistically. In this context this may seem a strange procedure, but when we come to composite LFs, statistical correction for fore ground galaxies is certainly important. For example if there is one bright galaxy in a cluster LF, the statistical correction states that there is not 1 galaxy, but only say 0.9 galaxy. In this case the correction has not much use. However if we consider the composite LF, there are many bright galaxies. If the statistical correction changes a value of 10 bright galaxies to 9 bright galaxies, this is significant. So this procedure was actually

Table 3.1: Fit results of LFs generated using a Monte Carlo method. Column (3), (4), (5) & (6) list the observed values. Column (7), (8) & (9) give the average of the estimated values as derived from the Fisher information.

(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)	(7)	(8)	(9)	(10)	
N	M_{lim}	σ_{M^*}	σ_α	$\rho(M^*, \alpha)$	$\sigma_{M^*(2)}$	$\overline{\sigma_{M^*}}$	$\overline{\sigma_\alpha}$	$\overline{\rho(M^*, \alpha)}$	#LFs	failures
50	-19.0	0.606	0.224	0.744	0.376	0.720	0.298	0.821	200	13
100	-19.0	0.466	0.190	0.773	0.290	0.503	0.205	0.826	200	1
200	-19.0	0.315	0.130	0.813	0.187	0.351	0.144	0.833	200	1
350	-19.0	0.269	0.107	0.771	0.171	0.269	0.107	0.834	500	0
500	-19.0	0.192	0.080	0.792	0.118	0.220	0.090	0.837	200	0
50	-20.0	0.558	0.289	0.770	0.337	0.724	0.449	0.871	200	24
100	-20.0	0.422	0.235	0.782	0.252	0.502	0.310	0.877	200	11
200	-20.0	0.312	0.192	0.864	0.160	0.355	0.216	0.880	200	2
350	-20.0	0.263	0.143	0.715	0.183	0.266	0.163	0.884	200	0
500	-20.0	0.193	0.119	0.853	0.101	0.222	0.136	0.885	200	0
40	-21.0	0.600	0.335	0.596	0.467	0.880	0.849	0.918	200	69
50	-21.0	0.540	0.309	0.755	0.386	0.769	0.755	0.921	200	63
100	-21.0	0.389	0.314	0.736	0.250	0.532	0.520	0.921	200	29
200	-21.0	0.315	0.278	0.781	0.195	0.376	0.364	0.922	200	14
350	-21.0	0.264	0.227	0.744	0.176	0.283	0.276	0.925	200	3
500	-21.0	0.246	0.200	0.737	0.165	0.237	0.229	0.926	200	0

adopted for the composite LF.

Excluding one bright galaxy per cluster has the advantage that it allows one to estimate the dependence of the fitted parameters on the brightest galaxy. Furthermore this way a lot of cD galaxies lying in the centers of many clusters are excluded from the fit. And cD galaxies are often taken to be of a different nature than other cluster members. For this reason Schechter (1976) advised to exclude cD galaxies from the sample when fitting the Schechter function to the data. It appears the fitted value depend very much on the exclusion of the BCM. What is worse: not only M^* , but also the best fitting α is different when the BCM is excluded. Hence, the use of α to search for variations at the faint end of the LF is very limited.

When one is forced to choose between the two sets of fitted values for M^* and α we advise to use the values obtained excluding the BCM if a cluster is of Bautz-Morgan type I or II, else use the values obtained by including the BCM. The Bautz-Morgan types for all clusters are listed in table I in Appendix B.

Inspecting all parameters $M^*(3)$ and α , one discovers a lot of anomalous values (say $\alpha < -1.6$ or $\alpha > -0.6$). This is caused by the fact that the magnitude limits are sometimes too bright to produce a good fit of α . There can also be another reason and that is that there is no real "knee" in the LF of a cluster. In that case a fit was produced with a very steep value of α and a bright value of M^* . An example is the LF of A1356, inspecting figure C.2 and table B.2 shows that the LF has not a Schechter form. In general, keeping α fixed produced more stable results.

In all cases it is wise not to rely solely on the Schechter parameters. One should also consult the figures of the LFs in Appendix C.

The bin-width used in the figures is 0.25mag . The error bars in the figures denote 1σ errors estimated by $\sigma = \sqrt{N_{ci} + (\delta N_{fi})^2}$, where N_{ci} is the number of galaxies in the i^{th} bin as expected from the best fitting Schechter and δN_{fi} is the expected noise in the field correction for that bin, following Lugger (1986) this is taken to be $\delta N_{fi} = \sqrt{N_{fi}}$ or $\delta N_{fi} = \frac{1}{2}N_{fi}$, whatever is the largest of the two.

According to our investigation of Monte Carlo generated LFs, the best estimation of M^* and α , if all LFs are drawn from a universal LF, is given by the median of the fitted parameters and not by the mean (see above). This way the influence of the "anomalous" values are reduced. The median value for the fitted Schechter parameters are $M^*(2) = -22.77$ and $M^*(3) = -22.74$ & $\alpha = -1.23$ if the BCMs are included. And $M^*(2) = -22.60$ and $M^*(3) = -22.41$ & $\alpha = -1.05$ if the BCMs are excluded. So excluding the BCM makes M^* fainter and flattens α . But the flattening of α is purely a result of the large correlation of M^* and α .

The composite LFs in the next chapter will give more reliable estimates of the "universal" LF, by then however we will have to abandon the idea of an "universal" LF from which all LFs are drawn. A first indication for this conclusion is that the dispersion in the fitted parameters is larger than the mean of the estimated variances, whereas the Monte Carlo runs indicated that the Fisher information overestimated the variances. However one can also maintain that those

Table 3.2: Comparison of Schechter parameters of this study with values found by others. Results are for the fits with the BCMs excluded.

Author:	Lugger			Oegerle			this study		
Abell	$M_R^*(3)$	α	$M_R^*(2)$	$M_R^*(3)$	α	$M_R^*(2)$	$M_R^*(3)$	α	$M_R^*(2)$
A1126				-22.72	-1.00	-23.07	-22.73	-1.42	-22.56
A1656	-22.43	-1.05	-22.70				-22.66	-1.35	-22.45
A1775				-23.19	-1.32	-23.05	-22.99	-1.30	-22.91
A1795				-22.36	-1.28	-22.32	-22.69	-1.44	-22.41
A2029				-22.35	-0.90	-22.87	-21.55	-0.31	-22.36
A2142				-22.11	-0.53	-23.00	-22.09	-0.71	-22.69
A2147	-22.61	-1.22	-22.66				-21.71	-0.84	-22.28
A2151	-23.16	-1.25	-23.06				-22.38	-0.95	-22.97
A2197	-23.28	-1.35	-22.93				-23.02	-1.36	-22.72
A2199	-22.26	-0.97	-22.69	-22.48	-1.05	-22.96	-21.72	-0.77	-22.60
Total Sample	-22.66	-1.24	-22.56	-22.49	-1.07	-22.87	-22.41	-1.05	-22.60

large deviations are due to uncertainties in the background contamination and other possible errors.

3.4 Comparison with Other Studies.

A number of cluster LFs investigated in the present study were also studied by others. We limit ourselves here to compare our results to the studies undertaken by Lugger (1986) and Oegerle *et al.*

Lugger (1986) used a sample of nine clusters LFs, all in the R passband. Oegerle *et al.* has LFs in the Thuan and Gunn system (r magnitudes). The conversion of the r passband to the R passband is approximately $R = r - 0.6$ (see Oegerle *et al.*(1989)).

In table 3.2 we list the fitted Schechter parameters for clusters our sample has in common with the studies mentioned above. Listed are the parameters obtained by excluding the BCM. At the bottom the values for the total sample are shown. These are the mean values of the studies by Oegerle *et al* and Lugger and the median values for the present study. Lugger used the χ^2 technique to obtain three parameter fits. All two parameter fits ($M_R^*(2)$) listed here are obtained using the maximum likelihood technique.

The mean/median values of all three studies are in good agreement with each other, given the different pass-bands and isophotal magnitudes used. The values for the two parameter fits are all within $0.2mag$ from $M^*(2) = -22.7$. We can add to this list the study of Dressler (1978), who found $M^* = -22.5$ in the F pass band and Colless (1989), who found $M^*(2) = -22.88$ (the B_J magnitude is converted to the R pass-band). Colless does not exclude BCMs, which

on average brightens M^* with $\sim 0.15\text{mag}$.

An inspection of table 3.2 learns that the magnitudes of this study are usually fainter than the values for $M^*(2)$ found by Lugger and Oegerle *et al.* This can be due to differences in magnitude systems, but there is also a possibility that differences in cluster areas, magnitude limits and background corrections caused this effect.

The mean/median value of α of this study is in good agreement with the value Oegerle *et al.* obtained and disagrees with $\alpha = -1.24$ found by Lugger. However this can be due to the strong correlation between M^* and α . Including the first ranked galaxy brightens M^* and consequently steepens α . It can also be that Lugger underestimated the average field contamination or that we overestimated it.

So it is very difficult to say anything definitive about the faint-end slope of the cluster luminosity function on basis of fits to the individual cluster LFs.

Furthermore the best fitting α is very sensitive to the magnitude limit (see also the section about the Monte Carlo runs). And there may be an additional effect due to different fitting techniques. So comparing LFs is plagued with the fact that the different studies are not done in a uniform manner. Still it seems there are clusters with intrinsic flat faint-end slopes. An example is A2199 which is measured in the present study to a rather faint absolute magnitude limit of $M_{lim} = -18.9$. All three studies in table 3.2 found a value flatter than the "standard" value of $\alpha = -1.25$.

3.5 A First Indication for the Richness Dependence of LFs

As mentioned above comparison of fitted parameters is difficult, due to the large correlation between the Schechter M^* and α . A small value of α may indicate a flat faint-end slope of a cluster LF, but it might as well indicate a lack of bright galaxies.

This does not mean that the Schechter parameters do not give any information at all. One should just not treat them separately. A good way treating them together is by showing them in a M^* versus α diagram.

Figure 3.1 shows two such diagrams. Best fitting values to most LFs are shown. The large correlation between the two parameters can be easily seen this way.

To see if there is any trend with richness, fits are given different symbols according to the richness of the cluster (see section 2.8 for the definition of richness used in this study).

There seems to be a trend for richer clusters to have parameter values lying more to the left side top of the diagram, whereas the parameters of poor cluster lie more to right hand bottom of the diagram. This is a first clue that the luminosity *distribution* of cluster galaxies depends on cluster richness! The effect is however subtle and will be better established in the next chapter when dealing with composite LFs.

Additional evidence is provided by the two-parameter fits. The mean values of $M^*(2)$ of the richest clusters (i.e. $RN > 60$ in table B.1 in appendix B) are: $M_R^*(2) = -23.03 \pm 0.43$ (mean value), $M_R^*(2) = -22.94$ (median value) this is including the brightest cluster member.

Figure 3.1: The fitted parameters M^* versus α . Different richness class clusters are given different symbols. The right hand figure shows fits with the brightest cluster members excluded. Some fits fall outside this figure.

The effect is even larger if the BCMs are excluded: $M_R^*(2) = -22.94 \pm 0.44$ (mean value) and $M_R^*(2) = -22.86$ (median value). So in the last case $M^*(2)$ is brighter than the median of the total sample by 0.26mag . Both values are still within each others standard deviation, but outside each others error of mean (which is 0.12mag for the rich cluster sample and 0.06mag for the total sample).

We also used another way to check the richness dependence of the LF. This method does not involve any fitting of parameters. Used is the ratio of the number of bright galaxies (having $M_R \leq -22.0$) to faint galaxies ($-22.0 < M_R \leq -21.0$). In table 3.3 the number of bright galaxies is denoted $N1$, the number faint galaxies by $N2$. The averaged values of the sample are listed and the total summed number of bright and faint galaxies are listed. The latter values offer the best statistics. Because the magnitude limits were not always fainter than $M_R = -21.0$, not all clusters are used for this test. The number of clusters in the sample is $N_{clusters}$. The number of galaxies is corrected for field contamination.

Both from the composite as from the mean of the individual cluster values it is appears that the ratio of number of faint over bright galaxies increases slightly with increasing richness (i.e. rich clusters have relatively more bright galaxies). However the dispersion in the relation is rather large.

Table 3.3: The statistics of the number of bright ($N1$) versus faint ($N2$) galaxies.

Sample	$N_{cluster}$	$\langle N1 \rangle$	$\langle N2 \rangle$	$\langle N2/N1 \rangle$	$N1_{tot}$	$N2_{tot}$	$N1_{tot}/N2_{tot}$
Total Sample	57	23.2	40.6	2.0 ± 0.8	1323.2	2313.6	1.7 ± 0.1
Poor ($RN \leq 42$)	28	14.7	27.9	2.1 ± 1.0	412.8	781.6	1.9 ± 0.1
Medium	21	25.4	45.8	1.9 ± 0.6	583.3	1054.5	1.8 ± 0.1
Rich ($RN > 65$)	6	54.5	79.6	1.4 ± 0.27	327.2	477.6	1.5 ± 0.1

Figure 3.2: Comparison of the cluster richness indicator used in this study and n^* (fitted with BCMs excluded and $\alpha = -1.25$).

Figure 3.3: The best fitting m^* as a function of $m - M$.

3.6 Is m^* a Good Distance Indicator?

In the past m^* has received some attention as a standard candle (e.g. Schechter & Press, 1976). The reason is that M^* is a distribution parameter, so it was thought to be richness independent. Other standard candles such as the first ranked galaxy and m_{10} are likely to be richness dependent, since at larger distances it is likely to select richer clusters (which have a larger contrast to the galaxy background) those distance indicators are likely to be biased towards brighter galaxies. This bias is known as the Schott-effect.

Another issue is, whether the first ranked galaxy is richness dependent. Or to put it differently, whether they are drawn from a luminosity *distribution* or from a different distribution. The reason is that giant ellipticals (cD and D galaxies) are found in clusters of different richness class and even in groups of galaxies. So may be their origin is of a different nature than other cluster galaxies.

Let us return to m^* as a distance indicator. From the previous sections it is clear that M^* is probably richness dependent. Even worse, comparing figure 2.8 (m_{10} versus $m - M$) with figure 3.3 shows that m_{10} seems to be a better distance indicator than m^* . This is quite surprising. The cause is probably not so much the richness dependence of M^* , but the uncertainties of fit.

Chapter 4

Further Evidence for a Non Universal LF

4.1 Composite LFs: an introduction.

In the previous chapter we showed that the LF may be richness dependent. In this chapter we introduce further evidence. This is done by combining the data of various cluster subsamples. Using these so called composite LFs has been done before. Luger (1986) used the composite LF of all clusters in her sample and tested whether the individual LFs could have been drawn from this composite LF, which serves as an hypothetical universal LF. Colless (1989) made composite LFs of different subsamples. These subsamples were based on cluster richness, Bautz-Morgan class, cluster velocity dispersion and position of the galaxies within the cluster. Our approach resembles that of Colless, only we have far more clusters at our disposal.

Using composite LFs has the obvious advantage that the statistics improves considerably. For instance, the composite LF of the total sample of 80 clusters is based on photometry of 9303 galaxies, correcting for field galaxies leaves us an expected number of 6726 cluster galaxies. Another advantage is that the statistical correction for the brightest galaxies makes more sense. Say that a cluster LF contributes one bright galaxy to a bin centered on $M_R = -24.0$ of width 0.25mag . Correcting all bins for field contamination, leaves say 0.9 instead of 1 galaxy in this particular bin. So there is a 10% chance that this galaxy is a field galaxy. Statistical correction does not make much sense in this case. There is one bright cluster galaxy or there is not. Making a composite LF improves the statistics of the bright galaxies considerably. Say the composite LF contains 10 galaxies in a bin around $M_R = -24.0$, then correcting this to 9 galaxies does make sense. One of the galaxies is then expected to be a galaxy in the fore-ground.

Figures with composite LFs were made by binning all data. The large number of galaxies allowed us to use a bin-width of 0.1mag . Only the first few bins concerning magnitudes brighter

Table 4.1: Bin-sizes and centerings for the first few bins.

center	bin-size
-25.5	1.0
-24.8	0.4
-24.5	0.2
-24.3	0.2
-24.1	0.195
-24.0	0.1

than $M_R = -24.0$ are represented with larger bin-widths. The bin-widths are tabulated in table 4.1. Because there is not a uniform absolute magnitude limit for all individual clusters, the bins are normalized according to the number of clusters contributing to a particular bin. So the composite LFs show the real (background corrected) number of galaxies contributing to a bin, but the first few bins are corrected for the larger bin-widths and the bins at fainter magnitude are normalized to correct for the fact that not all clusters contribute to those bins. We introduce a typical magnitude $M_{\frac{1}{2}}$, which is the magnitude for which the number of galaxies contributing to a bin is half the number of clusters in that (sub)sample. Typically $M_{\frac{1}{2}} = -20.7$.

Fits to the Schechter function were made using the maximum likelihood technique. Because not all clusters have the same absolute magnitude limit, the method is a little different from the method explained in chapter 3. The technique is explained in appendix A and resembles the maximum likelihood method used to determine the field luminosity function (see Efstathiou *et al.*, 1988). Again no binning is needed to make fits. The corrections for the variable bin-widths mentioned above, only refer to the figures of the composite LF not to the fits.

All fits to the composite LF were made adopting a minimal limiting magnitude $M_{lim} = -19.6$. However due to the variable magnitude limits of the individual clusters, the galaxies in the last few bins have less weight. The error bars in the figures only show the 1σ Poisson errors of the uncorrected number of galaxies.

4.2 The Composite LF of all 80 Clusters

The composite LF of our total sample contains galaxies from 80 clusters. The total number of galaxies is 9303 (i.e. to the limiting magnitudes of the individual clusters, but with a maximum limiting magnitude of $M = -19.6$). Correcting for the expected number of fore and background galaxies leaves 6726 cluster galaxies.

Fitting the Schechter distribution function to the composite LF resulted in $M_R^* = -22.64$, $\alpha = -1.21$ and $n^* = 49.0$. The value of α is close to the canonical value $\alpha = -1.25$. Using this value of α and fitting M_R^* gives $M_R^* = -22.63$. Compare these values to the median of the

Figure 4.1: The composite LF of all 80 clusters. On the left the LF including BCMs and on the right the LF excluding BCMs.

individual cluster fits: $M_R^* = -22.74$ and $\alpha = -1.23$. Due to the large number of galaxies the estimated variance in the parameters is small. The estimated errors are $\sigma(M^*) = 0.05\text{mag}$ and $\sigma(\alpha) = 0.03$.

Excluding the brightest cluster members (taken to be the brightest galaxy within 0.6Mpc of the cluster center), the best fitting Schechter parameters were: $M_R^* = -22.30$, $\alpha = -1.06$ and $N^* = 69.3$. Fixing $\alpha = -1.25$: $M_R^* = -22.49$. Note again the large correlation between α and M^* . Excluding the BCM does not change the faint-end slope, nevertheless the best fitting α changes! Note that without exclusion of the BCMs there is an excess of bright galaxies with respect to the best fitting Schechter function.

Both composite LFs are shown in figure 4.1.

We also tested the effect of the background contamination on the best fitting parameters. We changed the galaxy number counts by an overall amount of 25%. It appeared that $M^*(2)$ hardly changed ($< 0.01\text{mag}$). The three parameter fit were however different. With 25% more field galaxies $\alpha = -1.04$, 25% less field contamination made $\alpha = -1.34$. However varying the total number of field galaxies with 25% for all cluster fields is very different from a dispersion in the galaxy counts of 25% from field to field.

4.3 Composite LFs of different subsamples

Like Colless (1989) we formed different subsamples out of our total sample. These subsamples are based on richness, velocity dispersion and Bautz-Morgan class. Not for all clusters in our sample velocity dispersion are known. The Bautz-Morgan class is based on the presence of a dominating galaxy. That this will have an effect on the LF is rather obvious. Other cluster properties are thought to be more directly related to the merging and galaxy stripping rate in clusters (see chapter 1).

Table 4.2: Richness dependence : Fits to the composite luminosity function.

Sample	$n_{cluster}$	n_{gal}	$n_{gal-corr}$	$M_{\frac{1}{2}}$	$M^*(2)$	$n^*(2)$	$M^*(3)$	α	$n^*(3)$
Including the brightest cluster member:									
All	80	9303	6725.8	-20.7	-22.63	47.4	-22.64	-1.21	49.0
poor ($RN < 42$)	41	3532	2330.0	-20.8	-22.32	42.3	-22.52	-1.31	34.5
medium ($42 \leq RN < 65$)	30	3889	2815.2	-20.6	-22.71	47.5	-22.41	-1.04	70.3
rich ($RN > 65$)	9	1882	1580.6	-20.7	-22.94	80.5	-23.03	-1.26	75.5
Excluding the brightest cluster member:									
All	80	9223	6645.8	-20.7	-22.49	51.9	-22.30	-1.06	69.3
poor ($RN < 42$)	41	3491	2289.0	-20.8	-22.12	49.0	-22.01	-1.05	60.4
medium ($42 \leq RN < 65$)	30	3859	2785.2	-20.6	-22.58	51.4	-22.07	-0.84	97.1
rich ($RN > 65$)	9	1873	1571.6	-20.7	-22.85	84.9	-22.81	-1.18	93.6

4.3.1 The dependence of the LF on richness.

In chapter 3 we already saw that the LF of clusters seems to depend on richness. Composite LFs provide more convincing evidence.

Again we used the division of our total sample in three subsamples of different richness class. The richness classification is based on the richness definition described in chapter 2, namely the field corrected number of galaxies within the magnitude interval $-22.5 \leq M_R \leq -21.5$. This number we denote by RN . The three subsamples consist of clusters with richness $RN < 42$ (poor clusters), $42 \leq RN < 65$ (medium rich clusters) and $RN > 65$ (rich clusters). The richest clusters are all in the tail of the richness distribution (see section 2.8).

Figure C.13 shows the composite LFs for the three subsamples. The left-hand figures show LFs including the brightest cluster members, the right-hand figures show the same LFs, but excluding the BCMs. BCMs were defined as the brightest galaxy within a radius of $0.6 Mpc$ from the cluster center. Bright galaxies outside this radius are more likely to be foreground galaxies, which is corrected for statistically. Furthermore cD galaxies are always found near the center of a cluster.

The best fitting Schechter parameters are shown in table 4.2. From this table it is again clear that the fitted Schechter parameters greatly depend on the exclusion of the BCMs. Excluding them results in a fainter M^* and, due to the correlation between the two parameters, flattens α . This large correlation between the two parameters obscures the real form of the LF at the faint end. Again the estimated variances of M^* are very small ($\sigma(M^*) < 0.12$).

Nevertheless the trend remains that the richest clusters combine a brighter M^* with a steeper α . This trend was already apparent in the parameters of the fits to the individual

cluster LFs (see section 3.5). The richer the cluster the more the parameters are situated to the upper left corner of a M^* versus α diagram! Another way to say this is that the composite LF of the medium rich and rich cluster sample has an excess of bright galaxies with respect to the composite LF of the poor clusters sample.

To check if what is stated above is not merely an effect of one dominating cluster LF, we made fits to subsamples of the three subsamples. This was done using a Monte Carlo method. A random number was used to decide if a particular cluster would participate in a composite LF. For the total sample every cluster LF had a 50% chance to participate in the composite LF. So on average each composite LF was based on the LFs of 40 clusters. 100 random composite LFs were made this way. Plotting the fitted parameters in a M^* α diagram results in a sort of empirical error ellipse.

The same procedure was used for all three richness classes, with the exception that in case of the rich cluster sample the chance of selecting a cluster LF was effectively 70%. This was due to the fact that a smaller sample did not allow an automatic fitting procedure.

Figure C.14 show the four M^* - α diagrams. The position of the parameters of the composite LF of the total sample is indicated by a large circle. The fact that all randomly drawn composite LFs follow the trend of the sample they are drawn from indicates that the results are not a mere coincidence.

Figure C.13 and the fitted Schechter parameters shows that richer clusters have more bright galaxies than poor clusters. Checking the two-parameter fits shows this conclusion even holds if BCMs are excluded.

Another feature is that medium rich clusters have a flat faint-end logarithmic slope, whereas poor cluster have a rather steep faint-end ($\alpha = -1.3$). The faint-end of the composite LF of the richest clusters is again steep, but has a dip to a magnitude of $M_R = -20.5$. However the turn-up after $M_R \sim -20.5$ is caused solely by A1656 (Coma), the other clusters being at a larger distance and consequently having a rather bright absolute magnitude limit. It is not unlikely that the LFs of rich clusters have in general a flat faint-end. On the other hand the LF of Coma itself has a dip (see the LF of Coma in Appendix C and the paper of Luger (1986)). So it could be that all LFs of very rich cluster have a dip. No definitive conclusions can be made about the faint-end of the LF of very rich clusters.

Recall that our magnitude limit (see chapter 2) could have biased towards a steeper α for poor clusters. However the value of $M_{\frac{1}{2}}$ is about the same for the poor cluster sample as for the other samples. Figure 4.2 supports our confidence.

Be it a dip or a flat faint-end there seems to be a lack of galaxies in the magnitude range $-21.5 < M_R < -20.5$. So if all these features are caused by dynamical processes then it may be that stripping and merging are selective processes, mainly affecting galaxies in the above magnitude range.

Back to the poor clusters. It seems strange that poor clusters have a steep faint-end. This

Figure 4.2: Distribution of the magnitude limits for the three richness class samples. Note that the medium rich and the poor sample have about the same magnitude limit distribution.

does not fit in a trend from the LF of field galaxies (with $\alpha \sim -1.0$, see Loveday *et al.*, 1992) to poor clusters. It would be interesting to see if there is any trend in the LF from field galaxies, to galaxies in groups to poor clusters. Is there a gradually steepening of the faint-end of the LF from field to larger and larger groups?

In section 4.4 we will discuss the difference in LF for the inner region of the cluster and the outside region.

4.3.2 The velocity dispersion versus the LF of clusters

In the previous subsection evidence was presented that the LF of clusters depends on cluster richness. The evidence for a dependence of the LF on cluster velocity dispersion is less satisfying. First of all, we expect a correlation between clusters richness and the velocity dispersion, which is via the virial theorem correlated to the total mass of the cluster. An uncertainty is how the total cluster mass in galaxies is related to the total cluster mass (is this ratio constant?). Plotting the velocity dispersion against cluster richness does not reveal a very clear relation between the two (figure 4.3). Rich clusters always have a high velocity dispersion, but the opposite does not hold. It might be that the measured velocity dispersion overestimates the mass of a cluster (due to interlopers). Another source of error may be the non-uniform way of measuring velocity dispersions.

Given those reservations the composite LFs (figure C.15) do show some features. It seems that the LF of the clusters with low velocity dispersion clusters is better fitted by a Schechter function than the high velocity dispersion sample. The latter having a larger scatter at the bright-end of the LF. In section 4.5 we come back to this point.

This time however we cannot connect what the eyes see to a trend in the fitted parameters. M^* and α of the two samples are more or less the same, $M_R^*(2) = -22.74$ for low velocity

Table 4.3: Fits to composite LFs based on velocity dispersion and Bautz-Morgan class.

Sample	$n_{cluster}$	n_{gal}	$n_{gal-corr}$	$M_{\frac{1}{2}}$	$M^*(2)$	$n^*(2)$	$M^*(3)$	α	$n^*(3)$
Including the brightest cluster member:									
σ_v sample	34	5410	4061.8	-20.5	-22.71	52.3	-22.63	-1.20	58.2
$\sigma_v < 800 km/s$	19	2397	1721.9	-20.6	-22.74	41.3	-22.72	-1.23	42.9
$\sigma_v > 800 km/s$	15	3013	2339.8	-20.4	-22.72	63.2	-22.56	-1.18	76.1
$BM \leq II$	30	3750	2803.6	-20.7	-22.61	53.1	-22.57	-1.19	57.6
$BM > II$	50	5553	3922.2	-20.7	-22.65	44.0	-22.69	-1.23	44.0
Excluding the brightest cluster member:									
σ_v sample	34	5376	4027.8	-20.5	-22.60	55.6	-22.38	-1.10	74.9
$\sigma_v < 800 km/s$	19	2378	1702.9	-20.6	-22.63	43.8	-22.72	-1.16	52.5
$\sigma_v > 800 km/s$	15	2998	2324.8	-20.4	-22.61	67.1	-22.28	-1.05	101.3
$BM \leq II$	30	3720	2773.6	-20.7	-22.43	59.8	-22.09	-0.93	95.0

Figure 4.3: The cluster velocity dispersion (vertical axis) versus the cluster richness.

dispersion clusters and $M_R^*(2) = -22.72$ for clusters with high velocity dispersion ($\alpha = -1.25$).

4.3.3 The LF of clusters with different Bautz-Morgan class

The Bautz-Morgan (BM) class is based on the contrast between first-ranked and second-ranked galaxy. E.g. a BM I cluster is characterized by a dominant centrally located galaxy (often a cD galaxy). So per definition the LF of a BM I type cluster is different from the LF of a BM III cluster (having no dominant galaxy).

However, an interesting fact would be if the LF for different BM type cluster differ apart from the bright-end excess for BM I and BM II clusters.

The answer is that apart from an obvious excess for low BM type clusters resemble $BM > II$ type clusters at the faint-end. The best fitting Schechter parameters are not much different from each other. Surprising enough the $BM \leq II$ sample has $M_R^*(2) = -22.61$, whereas the $BM > II$ has a fainter M^* ($M_R^*(2) = -22.65$).

Note that this was not observed when we looked for different *richness* class clusters. Rich clusters do have a brighter M^* !

This is indirect evidence for the fact that rich clusters are not necessarily $BM \leq II$ clusters. On the contrary, table B.1 shows that only 4 of the richest clusters are in fact $BM \leq II$ clusters! (figure 4.4)

Another conclusion resembles the previous made conclusion concerning velocity dispersion, namely that the LF of $BM > II$ clusters are much better fitted by a Schechter function, especially at the bright-end.

The fact that the LF of $BM \leq II$ clusters is different of $BM > II$ cluster LFs (either with or without excluding BCMs) indicates that the presence of a very bright galaxy in a cluster is of influence on the whole LF.

Indicative is that A2029, which is the only very rich cluster of the BM I class, does have a rather faint M^* in comparison with the other rich clusters. This can be taken as evidence for "cannibalism".

4.4 Evidence for Luminosity Segregation

A well known phenomenon is the morphology density relation. Relatively more elliptical galaxies are found in the more dense regions of the universe. At the extreme ends: the field is dominated by spiral galaxies and rich clusters are dominated by elliptical and S0 galaxies.

This phenomenon is usually regarded to be caused by different galaxy formation histories. In denser regions merging of galaxies is more likely. In this scenario elliptical galaxies are seen as merging products.

An important question is when the merging process took place. Is this before the cluster was formed in groups of galaxies or after the collapse of the cluster region?

Keeping this in mind it is interesting to see if there is a difference in LF between the denser

Figure 4.4: A plot of the Bautz-Morgan class versus the richness. The Roman numbers are replaced by real numbers (so BM I-II is 1.5).

central regions and the outside regions of the cluster. Another reason is the so-called *luminosity segregation*. This means that more massive stellar systems loose there kinetic energy to the background mass. As a consequence, massive galaxies have a lower velocity with respect to the cluster center of mass and are more centrally located (hence the word segregation). This dynamical process is called dynamical friction.

We made composite LFs of the various subsamples for both the inside region of the cluster and the outside region. Note that an effect is even stronger in reality, since we are dealing here with the *projected* central region of the cluster (which is in deprojection a cylinder and not a sphere). The inner region was taken to be the region within $0.5Mpc$ from the cluster center. The LFs of both inner and outer regions are shown in figure C.16. From this figure it is clear that the outer regions resemble more the field cluster LF: a fainter M^* and a flatter faint-end slope! However this conclusion is less convincing for the richest clusters. Table 4.4 lists the fitted Schechter parameters. Note that the trend in M^* (brighter for richer clusters) is again present in both inside as outside LFs!

Remarkable is that both the inside and outside distribution of $BM > II$ clusters are rather well fit by a Schechter function. Only the parameters of the Schechter function are very much different, the magnitude difference being $\Delta M^*(2) > 0.6mag!$

To verify this conclusion we performed a Kolmogorov-Smirnov test. This statistical test does not involve binning of the data. To deal with non-cluster members we made a different division in inside and outside region. We defined inside and outside in such a way that both occupied the same area. This way the number of non-cluster members in both regions are expected to

Table 4.4: Position dependence : Fits to the composite luminosity function. Fits are made to the LF of the inner $0.5Mpc$ and the outside region.

Sample	n_{cl}	n_{gal}	$n_{gal-corr}$	$M_{\frac{1}{2}}$	$M^*(2)$	$n^*(2)$	$M^*(3)$	α	$n^*(3)$
All, $R \leq 0.5Mpc$	80	1564	1397.4	-20.7	-23.18	6.94	-23.43	-1.37	5.01
All, $R > 0.5Mpc$	80	7739	5328.4	-20.7	-22.46	42.6	-22.29	-1.06	55.8
Poor, $R \leq 0.5Mpc$	41	667	588.7	-20.8	-22.92	7.0	-23.32	-1.47	3.9
Poor, $R > 0.5Mpc$	41	2865	1741.3	-20.8	-22.07	38.9	-22.02	-1.07	44.7
Medium, $R \leq 0.5Mpc$	30	609	539.5	-20.6	-23.36	6.2	-23.37	-1.29	5.8
Medium, $R > 0.5Mpc$	30	3280	2275.7	-20.6	-22.52	43.8	-21.99	-0.80	84.8
Rich, $R \leq 0.5Mpc$	9	288	269.1	-20.7	-23.38	10.6	-23.66	-1.31	8.23
Rich, $R > 0.5Mpc$	9	1594	1311.5	-20.7	-22.84	71.4	-22.83	-1.21	75.1
$\sigma_v < 800km/s, R < 0.5Mpc$	19	425	379.7	-20.5	-23.12	7.2	-22.72	-1.01	12.0
$\sigma_v < 800km/s, R > 0.5Mpc$	19	1972	1342.2	-20.5	-22.61	34.9	-22.68	-1.28	32.6
$\sigma_v > 800km/s, R < 0.5Mpc$	15	481	438.3	-20.6	-23.28	8.7	-23.79	-1.47	4.3
$\sigma_v > 800km/s, R > 0.5Mpc$	15	2525	1895.2	-20.6	-22.20	90.6	-22.11	-0.96	98.6
$BM \leq II, R \leq 0.5Mpc$	30	654	590.6	-20.7	-23.21	7.61	-23.66	-1.45	4.17
$BM \leq II, R > 0.5Mpc$	30	3096	2213.0	-20.7	-22.40	48.5	-22.08	-0.94	75.7
$BM > II, R \leq 0.5Mpc$	50	910	806.5	-20.6	-23.16	6.5	-23.24	-1.30	5.8
$BM > II, R > 0.5Mpc$	50	4643	3115.4	-20.6	-22.49	39.1	-22.44	-1.14	44.9

Table 4.5: Confidence values from Kolmogorov-Smirnov tests. Tested was the hypotheses that inside and outside LF are the same. Here: inside $r \leq 1.1Mpc$, outside $1.1 < r \leq 1.5Mpc$.

Sample	N_{in}	N_{out}	$M_{bright} = -26$ %	$M_{bright} = -24$ %	$M_{bright} = -22.7$ %	$M_{bright} = -22$ %
all	3295	1858	0	0	1	32
poor	1260	703	0	0	7	49
medium	1359	753	0	0	1	11
rich	676	402	26	39	49	42
$BM \leq II$	1372	768	0	1	5	54
$BM > II$	1923	1090	0	0	7	14
$\sigma_v < 800km/s$	850	451	1	1	16	16
$\sigma_v > 800km/s$	913	489	2	4	20	89

be equal. Any uncertainty in the field-galaxy counts is thus removed! The price to be paid is that one is not free to choose the size of inside and outside region independently.

If the radius of the inside region is r_{ins} then the area of the outside region is given by $r_{ins} < r \leq \sqrt{2}r_{ins}$.

Table 4.4 list the confidence values for different brightness limits. The Kolmogorov-Smirnov test compared the distribution of inside and outside distribution in the magnitude range $M_{bright} \leq M_R \leq -20.7$, where the bright side limit, M_{bright} , was varied from $M_{bright} = -26$ to $M_{bright} = -22$. The inner region was the region within $1.1Mpc$ from the cluster center. The outer regions was the concentric region with a radius of $1.5Mpc$. Performing the test within the maximum allowable total region (with radius $2.0Mpc$) does not alter our conclusions.

N_{in} and N_{out} refer to the number of galaxies the test is based on. Given are the number of galaxies with $M_{bright} = -26$.

Even more interesting than those confidence values is *how* the inside and outside distribution are different from each other. A way to picture this is provided by the indicator the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test is based on: the maximum difference between the two *integrated* distributions. Plotting this difference shows from which magnitude on a distribution builds up an excess in comparison to the other. If both distributions would be the same the line would vary around 0. Note further that a non-horizontal slope indicates that the *differential* LFs of the inside and outside region are different.

Figure C.20 shows the difference between the inside and outside distribution for the three richness classes. It is clear that the poor cluster and medium rich cluster samples steadily build up an excess of galaxies brighter then $M > -22$. At fainter magnitudes the distributions become more the same. The maximum excess is located at $M_R \sim -22$, being $\sim 0.5mag$ fainter than M^* ! For the rich cluster sample the inside distribution has also an excess of bright

galaxies, setting in at brighter magnitudes than the other samples, but the excess is not so profound and noisier.

A second test was done but with a smaller inside and outside area ($r_{ins} = 0.7 Mpc$). The conclusions about the poor and medium rich clusters are not affected very much by this test (only the excess of galaxies in the inside region of poor cluster now sets in at a fainter magnitude). The rich clusters sample now does show an excess of galaxies, having a maximum at $M_R = -22.3$. The Kolmogorov-Smirnov test now indicated a confidence that both samples (inside vs outside) are identical of 11%. (see figure C.21)

Summarizing: there is an important difference between the LF in the center of clusters and the more outward regions of clusters. This difference is most apparent for poor and medium rich clusters, but seems more concentrated to the center of the cluster for rich clusters.

Surprisingly these differences are not only due to bright galaxies, but also to fainter galaxies of magnitudes $\sim M^*$. Luger (1986) also found differences in inside and outside LF in three clusters, but she found a lack of bright galaxies (apart from cD galaxies) in the center of clusters. Her findings were consistent with the theory that cD galaxies form at the cost of other bright galaxies (cannibalism). Our results are quite the opposite. The best explanation for what we find is the process of luminosity segregation.

4.5 Is the Cluster LF a Schechter Function?

Following Colless (1989) we tested how well the composite LFs of the different (sub)samples were fitted by the best fitting Schechter function to the composite LF of all 80 clusters (i.e a Schechter function with parameters $M_R^* = -22.73$ and $\alpha = -1.25$). The test was done using χ^2 statistics. The 1σ errors shown are only Poisson errors. Of all (sub)samples only the $BM > II$ sample appeared to be well fit by the Schechter function with a confidence of 44%. All other sample were rejected at 5% confidence.

The rejection is mainly caused by the excess of bright galaxies. Following Colless we tested over a limited magnitude range $-23.7 \leq M_R \leq -20.7$.

The results are listed in table 4.6. Clearly only the poor cluster sample, the $BM > II$ sample and the $\sigma_v < 800 km/s$ sample are well approximated by a Schechter function.

If one would think of the cluster LF as a distribution function that has evolved from the field LF, which is well approximated by a Schechter function, then the conclusion is that the LF of rich clusters and clusters with high velocity dispersion have evolved most from this "initial LF". However this scenario does not explain why the faint-end of the LF of poor clusters is steeper than that of the field LF.

Finally a remarkable feature has to be pointed out: almost all composite LFs show a sudden increase of galaxies at a magnitude $M_R \sim -22.7$. This feature is more or less present in all LFs, *except* the composite LF of $BM > II$ clusters. Note that both the medium rich and the rich cluster sample show this feature, but both samples are independent! The feature is most

Table 4.6: The confidence that a LF is fitted by a Schechter function with parameters $M_R^* = -22.63$ and $\alpha = -1.25$. Magnitude range: $-23.7 \leq M_R \leq -20.7$.

Sample	$P(\chi^2 \nu)$ BCMs included		$P(\chi^2 \nu)$ BCMs excluded	
	%		%	
All	9		3	
poor ($RN \leq 42$)	48		31	
medium ($42 < RN < 65$)	2		2	
rich ($RN > 64$)	0.3		0.4	
$BM \leq II$	8		7	
$BM > II$	70			
$BM > II$, inside	3			
$BM > II$, outside	89			
$\sigma_v < 800km/s$	70		70	
$\sigma_v > 800km/s$	0.08		0.02	

profound in the composite LF of the $BM \leq II$ sample: the bin centered around $M_R = -22.8$ counts 27 galaxies, the next bin around $M_R = -22.7$ contains 69 galaxies! So the number of galaxies suddenly more than doubles! We mention this for what it is worth. It may be a mere coincidence, a 3σ event.

Chapter 5

Summary & Discussion

This study of the cluster LF based on photometric data of more than 80 rich Abel clusters, shed some new light on the cluster LF. The most important conclusion to be made from this study is that *there seems not to be a universal cluster LF*. This conclusion is based especially on our investigation using composite LFs (chapter 4).

A related conclusion is that not all LFs are adequately approximated by the much used Schechter LF. There are however samples for which the Schechter function does give a good approximation to the LF. These samples are the poor cluster sample (based on our richness indicator $RN < 42$) the sample of clusters with $\sigma_v < 800 km/s$ and most of all the sample with Bautz-Morgan class $BM > II$. The latter sample has a best fitting Schechter function with parameters $M_R^* = -22.69$ and $\alpha = -1.23$. Note that the value for α is different from the α found for field galaxies ($\alpha \sim -1.0$). All other composite LFs show large deviations with respect to the best fitting Schechter function. These deviation are found on the bright-end of the LF.

Evidence that these deviations are not of statistical nature, is that there is a clear correlation between cluster richness and composite LF. The richer the cluster the brighter the best fitting M^* or the more the best fitting M^* and α are shifted to the upper left corner of a diagram with α on the vertical axis and M^* on the horizontal axis. Other ways to put this are: *rich clusters have relatively more bright galaxies*, or rich clusters have an excess of bright galaxies.

We also found that the LFs of (medium) rich clusters have a flat faint-end slope, whereas poor clusters have $\alpha \sim -1.3$. This does not fit in the trend from field LF (having also $\alpha \sim -1$). Our findings form evidence against the theory that all LFs are made of universal specific LFs, but with different mixed galaxy types. If these mixes are made according to the morphology density relation and if spiral rich LFs have a flat faint-end then rich clusters (containing a lot of elliptical galaxies) should have a steep faint-end. This is not what we observe!

The fact that the $BM \leq II$ composite LF is different from the $BM > II$ sample plus the fact that those cluster types are not very well correlated with cluster richness, indicates that the presence of a very bright galaxy in the center of a cluster has a profound influence on the LF (without first ranked galaxies that is).

A major outcome of this study is that the LF depends on the position of galaxies within the cluster. It appears that the inside region of clusters contains relatively more bright galaxies than the outside region of clusters. Surprisingly this excess builds up to a relatively faint magnitude of $M_R \sim -22$, which is $\sim 0.5\text{mag}$ fainter than M_R^* . This effect is most apparent for the poor cluster sample. The rich cluster sample also shows such an excess, but the contrast between inside and outside region is less and the excess seems to be more centrally located. This may also be the effect of a larger core region for rich clusters, because rich clusters may be more virialized than poor clusters.

So far we summarized our findings. More difficult is it to connect the results to a theory about dynamical processes.

We already concluded that the theory that every cluster LF could be build with universal type specific LFs can be excluded on basis of the trend in α mentioned above. We could however use this theory to explain that poor clusters have a steep faint-end slope. Note that even the poor clusters in our sample are relatively rich. Those clusters could have a higher fraction of elliptical galaxies than the field. So for poor clusters the steep faint-end can be explained by the type mixing theory of Gregory & Thompson (1984).

Going now to richer and richer clusters this theory does not explain anymore the slope of the LF. For these clusters we have to explain the form of the LF by dynamical processes. Both merging and tidal stripping could explain the flat faint-end slope. Stripping is the most effective process for flattening the faint-end slope. Merging has relatively more effects on the bright-end side of the LF. For example if two L^* merge this has no dramatic effect on the number counts of magnitude $\sim M^*$, but a new bright galaxy does show up and this has a brightening effect on the fitted M^* .

The brightening of M^* may be explained by merging. The question if merging took place in a pre-cluster phase or during the cluster's lifetime cannot be solved. The fact that most rich clusters are not BM I type clusters, may be an indication that those clusters are formed by the merging of smaller clusters.

Finally a word about the difference in inside and outside luminosity distribution. It seems that luminosity segregation is the most likely process for explaining our observations. The reason is that merging (which might give an additional effect) is more likely to effect the very bright end of the LF, whereas the effect we measure is effective up to magnitudes of $M_R \sim -22$. If the effect is truly caused by luminosity segregation then this is a very important discovery, since the amount of luminosity segregation depends on the mass of a cluster initially bound to galaxies (Merritt, 1984 & 1985). The more luminosity segregation the more cluster mass was originally attached to galaxies.

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Appendix A

Maximum Likelihood Estimators for M^* and α .

A.1 Maximum Likelihood Estimators.

We start with the Schechter function:

$$n(l) dl = n^* \exp(-\frac{l}{l^*}) (\frac{l}{l^*})^\alpha d\frac{l}{l^*} \quad (\text{A.1})$$

The total number of expected galaxies with luminosity $l > l_{lim}$ is:

$$N_{exp} = \int_{l_{lim}}^{\infty} n(l) dl = n^* \Gamma(\alpha + 1, \frac{l_{lim}}{l^*}), \quad (\text{A.2})$$

where $\Gamma(a, x)$ is the incomplete gamma function.

The statistical distribution function $f(l/l^*)$ corresponding with the Schechter function with a limiting luminosity l_{lim} is given by:

$$f(\frac{l}{l^*}) = \frac{\exp(-\frac{l}{l^*}) (\frac{l}{l^*})^\alpha}{\Gamma(\alpha + 1, \frac{l_{lim}}{l^*})} \quad (\text{A.3})$$

The log likelihood function $\ln \mathcal{L}$ is now defined by:

$$\ln \mathcal{L} = \sum_{i=1}^N \ln f(l_i/l^*) \quad (\text{A.4})$$

where N is the total number of galaxies in the list with $l > l_{lim}$. Partly following Schechter and Press (1976), we introduce:

$$\lambda_i = l_i/l_{lim}, \quad \lambda^* = l^*/l_{lim}, \quad \Gamma() = \Gamma(\alpha + 1, 1/\lambda^*).$$

Partial derivatives of the incomplete gamma function we denote with a subscript. So $\Gamma_\alpha() = \frac{\partial \Gamma(\alpha+1, 1/\lambda^*)}{\partial \alpha}$. Mean values are denoted with a bar.

Writing out (A.4) we get

$$\ln \mathcal{L} = -\frac{N\bar{\lambda}}{\lambda^*} + (\alpha + 1) \sum_{i=1}^N \ln \frac{\lambda_i}{\lambda^*} - N \ln \Gamma(). \quad (\text{A.5})$$

The Maximum Likelihood estimators are now defined as the estimators that maximize $\ln \mathcal{L}$. So we require

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial \lambda^*} = \frac{N\bar{\lambda}}{\lambda^{*2}} - \frac{(\alpha + 1)N}{\lambda^*} - \frac{N\Gamma_{\lambda^*}()}{\Gamma()} = 0 \quad (\text{A.6})$$

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial \alpha} = \sum_{i=0}^N \ln \frac{\lambda_i}{\lambda^*} - \frac{N\Gamma_\alpha()}{\Gamma()} = 0 \quad (\text{A.7})$$

With $\Gamma()_{\lambda^*} = e^{-\frac{1}{\lambda^*}}(\frac{1}{\lambda^*})^{\alpha+2}$. Note that there is no analytical expression for $\Gamma_\alpha()$, so it must be done numerically. Note further that for a two parameter fit (fitting l^* and n^*) only (A.6) has to be calculated. Finally note that n^* is fitted by requiring that the expected number of galaxies equals the actual number of galaxies:

$$N = n^* \Gamma(\alpha + 1, \frac{l_{lim}}{l^*}). \quad (\text{A.8})$$

The second order derivatives of equation A.5 are:

$$\frac{\partial^2 \mathcal{L}}{\partial \lambda^{*2}} = -2\frac{N\bar{\lambda}}{\lambda^{*3}} + \frac{(\alpha + 1)N}{\lambda^{*2}} - N \frac{\Gamma_{\lambda^*\lambda^*}()\Gamma() - \Gamma_{\lambda^*}()\Gamma_{\lambda^*}()}{\Gamma^2()} \quad (\text{A.9})$$

$$\frac{\partial^2 \mathcal{L}}{\partial \lambda^* \partial \alpha} = \frac{\partial^2 \mathcal{L}}{\partial \alpha \partial \lambda^*} = -\frac{N}{\lambda^*} - N \frac{\Gamma_{\lambda^*\alpha}()\Gamma() - \Gamma_{\lambda^*}()\Gamma_\alpha()}{\Gamma^2()} \quad (\text{A.10})$$

$$\frac{\partial^2 \mathcal{L}}{\partial \alpha^2} = -N \frac{\Gamma_{\alpha\alpha}()\Gamma() - \Gamma_\alpha()\Gamma_\alpha()}{\Gamma^2()} \quad (\text{A.11})$$

Where $\Gamma_{\lambda^*\lambda^*}() = e^{-\frac{1}{\lambda^*}}(\frac{1}{\lambda^*})^{\alpha+2}(\frac{1}{\lambda^{*2}} - \frac{\alpha+2}{\lambda^*})$ and $\Gamma_{\lambda^*\alpha}() = -\ln \lambda^* e^{-\frac{1}{\lambda^*}}(\frac{1}{\lambda^*})^{\alpha+2}$.

These second order derivatives are needed to make the actual fit. We have done this using the Newton-Raphson method (we used the routine “mnewt” from *Numerical Recipes*, Press *et al.*).

The second order derivatives are also important for another reason: the negative of the second derivative matrix forms the so called *Fisher-information*. The inverse of the Fisher-information is an estimator for the variance matrix. The variance matrix is a matrix containing $\sigma^2(\lambda^*)$ and $\sigma^2(\alpha)$ on the diagonal and $cov(\lambda^*, \alpha)$ on the off-diagonal. Inverting the Fisher-information matrix shows $\sigma^2(\lambda^*) \propto \frac{1}{N}$, $\sigma^2(\alpha) \propto \frac{1}{N}$ and $cov(\lambda^*, \alpha) \propto \frac{1}{N}$.

A.2 Fitting the Joint Luminosity Function.

The fitting method for the joint luminosity function is the same as the maximum likelihood method described above except (A.2) has to be replaced by

$$N_{exp} = \sum_j n^* \Gamma(\alpha + 1, \frac{l_{min,j}}{l^*}) \quad (\text{A.12})$$

where \sum_j indicates the summation over all clusters with limiting luminosity $l_{min,j}$, varying from cluster to cluster. So in all maximum likelihood equations we have to replace the incomplete gamma function and its derivatives by the sums over gamma functions with different l_{lim} .

A.3 Corrections for Field Galaxies

Correcting for field contamination is quite straight forward. First note that the input for this maximum likelihood method consists of: N , l_{lim} , $\sum_{i=1}^N l_i$ and $\sum_{i=1}^N \ln l_i$. So we can correct for field contamination by subtracting the values of N , $\sum_i l_i$ and $\sum_i \ln l_i$ as expected from field number counts. This was already pointed out by Schechter & Press (1976), but they did not need $\sum_i \ln l_i$, because they were only interested in m^* .

We assume for the field number density

$$\log N_f = Am + B \quad (\text{A.13})$$

where N_f is the number of field galaxies per magnitude interval per square arc-seconds. As described in section 2.7 for A and B we use values derived from field number counts by Metcalfe *et al.* (1991).

Translating the number counts to a distribution function in magnitude or in luminosity we get

$$n(m)dm = 10^{Am+B} dm \quad (\text{A.14})$$

or

$$n(l)dl = \left(\frac{l}{l_0}\right)^{-2.5A-1} 10^{B+Am_0} k dl, \quad (\text{A.15})$$

where $k = 2.5/\ln 10$ and m_0 the reference magnitude. So the number of galaxies is corrected by subtracting n_f , this being

$$n_f = \int_{m_1}^{m_n} 10^{Am+B} dm = 10^B \int_{m_1}^{m_n} e^{A \ln 10 m} dm = \frac{10^A m_n - 10^A m_1}{A \ln 10} 10^B \quad (\text{A.16})$$

To estimate the total amount of light l_{tot} contributed by field galaxies per unit area one finds

$$\begin{aligned}
 l_{tot} &= \int_{m_1}^{m_n} l(m) n(m) dm = \int_{m_1}^{m_n} 10^{-0.4(m-m_0)} 10^{Am+B} dm = \\
 &= 10^{B+0.4m_0} \int_{m_1}^{m_n} e^{(A-0.4) \ln 10 m} dm = \\
 &= \frac{e^{(A-0.4) \ln 10 m_n} - e^{(A-0.4) \ln 10 m_1}}{(A-0.4) \ln 10} 10^{B+m_0}
 \end{aligned} \tag{A.17}$$

The expected field contribution to $\sum_i \ln l_i$ is

$$\begin{aligned}
 \ln l_{tot} &= \int_{l_n}^{l_1} \ln l n(l) dl = \\
 &= \frac{l_1^{-2.5A} (\ln l_1 + \frac{1}{2.5A}) - l_n^{-2.5A} (\ln l_n + \frac{1}{2.5A})}{2.5A} 10^{B+Am_0} k.
 \end{aligned} \tag{A.18}$$

The only disadvantage of this method is that the field number counts varies strongly from field to field, an extra error that can not easily be incorporated in the Fisher information. Although the fact that N changes to $N - n_f$ results in larger values for the variance matrix.

Appendix B

Tables

This appendix contains tables with information about all 80 clusters. Table B.1 list general information about the sample. Table B.2 and B.3 lists the fitted Schechter parameters.

Additional information concerning table B.1: the column N_z list how many redshifts were used to derive the redshift (z) and the velocity dispersion (σ_v). n_{corr} is the number of galaxies used in this study with correction for the expected amount of field contamination. These numbers are calculated for the magnitude limit m_{lim} also listed in this table. RN is the richness value , based on the richness indicator explained in chapter 2.

Table B.1: The sample.

Abell	z	N_z	σ_v km/s	n	n_{corr}	rad	RN	m_{lim}	M_{lim}	BM Type
A978	0.0527	2		137	101.5	1.83	44.9	17.44	-20.22	II
A1020	0.0650	1		95	65.4	1.92	33.9	17.55	-20.56	II-III
A1126	0.0852	3		51	34.6	2.00	33.4	17.44	-21.31	I-II
A1169	0.0582	1		65	45.2	2.00	24.3	17.01	-20.84	III
A1187	0.0791	1		68	52.1	2.00	42.1	17.30	-21.27	III
A1190	0.0794	1		68	52.3	2.00	50.2	17.30	-21.28	II
A1213	0.0468	12	598	60	45.8	2.00	35.8	16.40	-20.95	III
A1216	0.0524	1		157	111.2	1.86	20.4	17.60	-20.01	III
A1238	0.0716	1		99	71.0	2.00	36.9	17.59	-20.75	III
A1317	0.0700	3		121	91.0	2.00	46.1	17.60	-20.71	I-II
A1318	0.0566	6	284	56	39.5	1.70	33.1	17.05	-20.74	II
A1337	0.0826	2		45	23.5	2.00	20.1	17.60	-21.07	III
A1344	0.0770	2		65	35.3	2.00	21.4	17.75	-20.78	II-III
A1346	0.0970	1		56	42.8	2.00	50.2	17.50	-21.55	II-III
A1356	0.0698	2		134	89.1	2.00	29.2	17.91	-20.37	II-III
A1365	0.0763	1		37	25.8	2.00	27.9	17.00	-21.49	III
A1377	0.0514	13	488	85	62.9	1.92	42.3	16.94	-20.63	III
A1383	0.0603	5	395	147	96.4	2.00	33.0	17.79	-20.15	III
A1385	0.0831	2		39	15.4	2.00	10.9	17.70	-20.99	III
A1399	0.0913	1		60	45.6	2.00	43.7	17.50	-21.41	III
A1412	0.0839	1		107	75.5	2.00	50.8	17.94	-20.80	III
A1424	0.0770	2		100	72.2	2.00	46.4	17.70	-20.81	III
A1436	0.0646	4		98	67.3	2.00	46.9	17.50	-20.60	III
A1468	0.0844	2		54	33.6	2.00	27.4	17.60	-21.12	I
A1474	0.0791	2		93	59.9	2.00	29.8	17.88	-20.69	III
A1496	0.0941	2		44	29.8	2.00	33.4	17.50	-21.48	III
A1526	0.0799	4		114	96.1	2.00	84.0	17.40	-21.19	III
A1552	0.0843	3		95	71.5	2.00	57.9	17.70	-21.02	II
A1609	0.0891	1		23	12.0	2.00	18.5	17.20	-21.65	II-III
A1630	0.0649	1		28	14.3	2.00	13.7	16.90	-21.21	II-III
A1644	0.0473	92	933	174	118.1	1.73	52.0	17.70	-19.71	II
A1650	0.0845	2		114	88.0	2.00	54.7	17.80	-20.93	I-II

Table B.1: The sample.

Abell	z	N_z	σ_v <i>km/s</i>	n	n_{corr}	rad	RN	m_{lim}	M_{lim}	BM Type
A1656	0.0232	226	1140	648	579.8	2.00	135.1	16.50	-19.27	II
A1668	0.0648	1		132	101.5	2.00	43.6	17.50	-20.60	II
A1691	0.0722	1		67	45.9	2.00	34.8	17.38	-20.98	II
A1749	0.0590	2	933	39	19.5	2.00	17.4	17.00	-20.89	II
A1767	0.0701	16		96	65.5	2.00	39.3	17.62	-20.67	II
A1773	0.0776	1		135	107.2	2.00	65.5	17.70	-20.82	III
A1775	0.0717	28	1594	123	86.1	2.00	46.9	17.80	-20.54	I
A1780	0.0780	2		151	108.8	2.00	58.6	18.05	-20.49	III
A1793	0.0849	1		35	17.8	2.00	17.5	17.50	-21.24	III
A1795	0.0616	49	896	129	93.2	2.00	38.1	17.54	-20.45	I
A1809	0.0788	11	249	126	99.0	2.00	60.1	17.70	-20.86	II
A1827	0.0668	1		43	25.7	2.00	22.5	17.10	-21.07	II
A1831	0.0613	11	316	150	115.9	2.00	31.0	17.50	-20.48	III
A1892	0.0910	1		45	25.9	2.00	25.0	17.70	-21.25	III
A1904	0.0708	24	803	126	90.9	2.00	44.8	17.74	-20.57	II-III
A1913	0.0528	16	656	141	100.4	1.85	44.0	17.52	-20.11	III
A1927	0.0740	1		57	30.4	2.00	19.3	17.60	-20.81	I-II
A1939	0.0883	5		39	24.3	2.00	25.6	17.42	-21.41	II-III
A1983	0.0449	74	846	119	89.1	2.00	38.0	16.91	-20.35	III
A1991	0.0579	15	510	57	44.8	1.73	38.4	16.83	-21.01	I
A2018	0.0878	2		114	82.9	2.00	48.0	17.99	-20.83	II
A2022	0.0581	3		84	57.7	2.00	31.4	17.21	-20.64	III
A2028	0.0776	20	434	65	49.7	2.00	47.7	17.24	-21.29	II-III
A2029	0.0767	59	1411	209	176.8	2.00	97.6	17.80	-20.70	I
A2040	0.0456	21	367	64	49.2	2.00	35.4	16.38	-20.92	III
A2048	0.0945	1		83	62.5	2.00	56.6	17.79	-21.23	III
A2056	0.0804	1		68	42.9	2.00	27.0	17.70	-20.91	II-III
A2061	0.0782	20	730	152	118.7	2.00	88.4	17.86	-20.68	III
A2067	0.0748	12	761	90	60.5	2.00	35.4	17.71	-20.73	III
A2079	0.0656	29	639	160	130.0	2.00	63.8	17.50	-20.63	II-III
A2089	0.0733	20	551	92	56.0	2.00	28.6	17.82	-20.57	II
A2092	0.0669	18	504	68	39.5	2.00	24.0	17.50	-20.68	II-III
A2107	0.0421	20	536	203	143.3	1.58	22.1	17.71	-19.40	I

Table B.1: The sample.

Abell	z	N_z	σ_v <i>km/s</i>	n	n_{corr}	rad	RN	m_{lim}	M_{lim}	BM Type
A2110	0.0980	2		42	24.8	2.00	29.6	17.70	-21.38	I-II
A2122	0.0651	1		106	77.0	2.00	46.4	17.46	-20.66	II-III
A2142	0.0899	15	1241	146	103.6	2.00	55.1	18.28	-20.62	II
A2147	0.0356	30	1081	245	185.0	2.00	46.6	17.08	-19.68	III
A2151	0.0368	99	760	265	169.1	2.00	57.5	17.50	-19.34	III
A2152	0.0374	22	1346	548	351.9	2.00	37.4	18.09	-18.79	III
A2175	0.0968	2		121	95.3	2.00	72.6	18.00	-21.08	II
A2197	0.0308	46	550	356	179.3	2.00	46.2	17.70	-18.74	III
A2198	0.0798	2		93	54.1	2.00	23.0	18.03	-20.59	III
A2199	0.0299	71	823	320	174.7	2.00	37.3	17.50	-18.87	I
A2244	0.0968	27	1240	175	157.3	2.00	152.5	17.70	-21.40	I-II
A2245	0.0850	4		121	87.5	2.00	42.0	18.00	-20.79	II
A2250	0.0654	18	693	253	195.9	2.00	50.3	18.00	-20.18	III
A2255	0.0800	35	1221	259	215.9	2.00	122.6	18.10	-20.55	II-III
A2256	0.0581	90	1270	169	128.5	1.99	80.0	17.55	-20.36	II-III

Table B.2: Fits to the Schechterfunction. Brightest cluster galaxies are included.

Abell	$M^*(2)$	σ_{M^*}	$n^*(2)$	$M^*(3)$	σ_{M^*}	α	σ_α	$cov(M^*, \alpha)$	$n^*(3)$
A978	-22.39	0.27	51.36	-21.40	0.31	-0.26	0.40	0.12	142.69
A1020	-22.45	0.30	40.83	-21.99	0.50	-0.83	0.49	0.23	71.86
A1126	-22.92	0.34	27.90	-24.48	1.91	-2.09	0.49	0.79	1.99
A1169	-22.46	0.32	36.74	-22.11	0.64	-0.90	0.67	0.39	56.71
A1187	-23.16	0.31	32.04	-23.93	1.02	-1.72	0.40	0.36	9.68
A1190	-22.76	0.30	47.99	-25.64	3.36	-2.42	0.35	0.92	0.29
A1213	-23.04	0.33	25.29	-22.12	0.48	-0.31	0.62	0.28	66.16
A1216	-21.27	0.25	116.24	-24.04	2.25	-2.48	0.27	0.48	0.73
A1238	-22.23	0.28	60.83	-22.16	0.59	-1.19	0.52	0.29	66.20
A1317	-22.63	0.27	56.75	-23.51	0.81	-1.76	0.30	0.21	14.38
A1318	-23.99	0.36	10.89	-24.29	0.90	-1.38	0.30	0.22	7.29
A1337	-23.28	0.39	11.68	-24.64	2.01	-1.87	0.47	0.77	1.41
A1344	-22.87	0.34	20.86	-24.28	1.65	-1.92	0.40	0.54	2.24
A1346	-22.88	0.32	42.74	-21.96	0.52	0.06	0.97	0.48	84.98
A1356	-23.41	0.29	26.88	-28.31	6.85	-2.11	0.14	0.42	0.03
A1365	-23.31	0.37	16.85	-22.26	0.61	-0.01	0.98	0.56	42.52
A1377	-23.17	0.31	25.28	-22.30	0.42	-0.54	0.41	0.16	68.67
A1383	-22.41	0.27	46.16	-22.59	0.55	-1.36	0.29	0.14	35.83
A1385	-22.70	0.42	10.97	-24.19	2.74	-2.03	0.70	1.62	0.93
A1399	-22.69	0.31	47.01	-21.70	0.49	0.23	0.98	0.46	89.31
A1412	-22.36	0.28	61.99	-21.73	0.44	-0.53	0.58	0.24	123.00
A1424	-22.50	0.29	52.14	-21.97	0.47	-0.71	0.53	0.23	97.00
A1436	-23.32	0.31	24.23	-22.16	0.36	-0.26	0.40	0.13	82.74
A1468	-23.20	0.35	19.56	-22.95	0.75	-1.05	0.59	0.40	27.15
A1474	-22.72	0.31	33.45	-22.69	0.63	-1.22	0.43	0.24	35.31
A1496	-23.25	0.36	21.12	-22.87	0.76	-0.89	0.76	0.54	34.17
A1526	-23.99	0.28	33.50	-24.07	0.52	-1.29	0.23	0.10	29.98
A1552	-23.50	0.30	29.88	-24.21	0.82	-1.61	0.27	0.19	10.49
A1609	-23.75	0.45	6.74	-25.54	3.49	-2.01	0.64	1.78	0.39
A1630	-22.83	0.42	11.21	-22.05	0.92	-0.33	1.34	1.16	24.61
A1644	-22.94	0.27	32.75	-22.69	0.40	-1.12	0.19	0.07	45.47
A1650	-22.49	0.27	70.20	-22.64	0.58	-1.37	0.43	0.23	56.79

Table B.2: Fits to the Schechterfunction. Brightest cluster galaxies are included.

Abell	$M^*(2)$	σ_{M^*}	$n^*(2)$	$M^*(3)$	σ_{M^*}	α	σ_α	$cov(M^*, \alpha)$	$n^*(3)$
A1656	-22.49	0.18	159.70	-22.76	0.23	-1.37	0.08	0.01	110.64
A1668	-21.98	0.26	95.01	-22.17	0.56	-1.42	0.43	0.22	72.23
A1691	-23.04	0.33	25.90	-22.49	0.56	-0.76	0.55	0.29	50.65
A1749	-22.96	0.41	10.56	-23.11	1.21	-1.35	0.70	0.75	8.53
A1767	-22.50	0.30	42.37	-22.02	0.50	-0.80	0.51	0.23	76.28
A1773	-23.22	0.27	47.04	-25.59	1.59	-2.04	0.18	0.21	1.26
A1775	-23.02	0.29	35.76	-23.18	0.57	-1.34	0.28	0.14	28.72
A1780	-22.50	0.26	61.03	-21.86	0.35	-0.65	0.38	0.12	131.09
A1793	-22.39	0.38	24.42	-23.40	2.03	-2.04	0.96	1.76	4.23
A1795	-22.58	0.27	49.25	-23.16	0.68	-1.59	0.28	0.17	20.74
A1809	-22.82	0.27	58.25	-24.40	1.12	-1.99	0.24	0.22	4.56
A1827	-23.53	0.39	10.83	-22.99	0.76	-0.84	0.61	0.41	21.41
A1831	-22.11	0.26	87.64	-23.21	0.82	-1.92	0.29	0.20	14.41
A1892	-22.46	0.36	31.11	-22.21	0.90	-0.96	1.08	0.91	42.31
A1904	-23.19	0.28	36.35	-23.90	0.72	-1.59	0.23	0.14	13.05
A1913	-23.06	0.28	32.22	-23.01	0.48	-1.22	0.22	0.09	34.48
A1927	-23.06	0.36	15.25	-23.90	1.33	-1.69	0.44	0.50	4.34
A1939	-22.70	0.37	24.80	-24.68	3.01	-2.31	0.63	1.61	0.72
A1983	-22.45	0.28	47.28	-21.54	0.35	-0.35	0.44	0.14	123.89
A1991	-22.65	0.32	34.76	-22.52	0.71	-1.13	0.62	0.41	41.65
A2018	-22.55	0.28	58.19	-23.26	0.79	-1.72	0.35	0.25	19.04
A2022	-23.12	0.31	24.72	-23.09	0.63	-1.23	0.35	0.20	25.72
A2028	-23.53	0.32	23.99	-23.24	0.61	-1.03	0.45	0.25	35.17
A2029	-22.47	0.23	118.49	-22.10	0.32	-0.91	0.31	0.09	189.67
A2040	-22.65	0.31	35.22	-22.06	0.55	-0.65	0.64	0.33	69.01
A2048	-23.49	0.30	30.55	-22.91	0.48	-0.77	0.44	0.19	62.49
A2056	-22.65	0.33	29.88	-22.60	0.75	-1.21	0.58	0.40	31.86
A2061	-23.37	0.27	43.99	-22.72	0.33	-0.78	0.27	0.08	98.04
A2067	-22.49	0.30	43.70	-22.79	0.74	-1.47	0.45	0.30	28.17
A2079	-22.85	0.25	64.60	-23.22	0.52	-1.48	0.24	0.11	37.59
A2089	-22.70	0.31	29.84	-22.93	0.74	-1.40	0.39	0.26	21.34
A2092	-22.64	0.34	23.02	-21.81	0.50	-0.39	0.68	0.34	56.41
A2107	-21.80	0.25	62.96	-22.02	0.46	-1.38	0.22	0.09	45.78

Table B.2: Fits to the Schechterfunction. Brightest cluster galaxies are included.

Abell	$M^*(2)$	σ_{M^*}	$n^*(2)$	$M^*(3)$	σ_{M^*}	α	σ_α	$cov(M^*, \alpha)$	$n^*(3)$
A2110	-22.82	0.37	23.18	-22.92	1.07	-1.34	0.87	0.86	19.97
A2122	-22.40	0.28	55.60	-22.03	0.48	-0.89	0.48	0.21	88.82
A2142	-22.78	0.27	52.73	-22.28	0.39	-0.84	0.34	0.12	97.97
A2147	-22.34	0.24	68.93	-21.86	0.29	-0.92	0.20	0.05	127.92
A2151	-23.03	0.25	37.41	-22.48	0.30	-0.98	0.15	0.04	74.50
A2152	-21.61	0.20	120.55	-22.66	0.43	-1.68	0.10	0.03	26.64
A2175	-22.94	0.27	60.19	-22.56	0.43	-0.91	0.40	0.16	97.14
A2197	-22.77	0.25	34.05	-23.06	0.43	-1.35	0.11	0.04	23.39
A2198	-21.85	0.30	56.71	-22.42	0.94	-1.72	0.58	0.49	23.08
A2199	-22.63	0.25	37.28	-21.74	0.25	-0.77	0.15	0.03	107.92
A2244	-23.04	0.24	119.20	-23.27	0.45	-1.44	0.30	0.12	84.55
A2245	-22.33	0.27	71.24	-23.12	0.81	-1.79	0.37	0.27	19.99
A2250	-22.32	0.23	101.54	-23.54	0.65	-1.84	0.17	0.09	15.19
A2255	-22.91	0.23	96.78	-22.58	0.29	-1.01	0.21	0.05	148.53
A2256	-23.21	0.26	42.99	-22.39	0.30	-0.63	0.26	0.07	117.60
mean	-22.79	0.30	45.6	-22.99	0.90	-1.22	0.45	0.36	49.12
	± 0.49			± 1.12		± 0.59			
median	-22.77			-22.74		-1.23			
	± 0.49			± 1.16		± 0.60			

Table B.3: Fits to the Schechterfunction. Brightest cluster galaxies are excluded.

Abell	$M^*(2)$	σ_{M^*}	$n^*(2)$	$M^*(3)$	σ_{M^*}	α	σ_α	$cov(M^*, \alpha)$	$n^*(3)$
A978	-22.34	0.27	52.59	-21.33	0.31	-0.20	0.42	0.12	146.07
A1020	-22.40	0.30	41.45	-21.99	0.52	-0.87	0.50	0.24	69.34
A1126	-22.56	0.33	38.12	-22.73	0.97	-1.42	0.81	0.73	29.47
A1169	-22.39	0.32	38.28	-22.08	0.66	-0.93	0.70	0.43	56.53
A1187	-22.97	0.31	36.38	-23.43	0.88	-1.58	0.48	0.38	18.09
A1190	-22.53	0.30	58.16	-24.90	2.61	-2.44	0.43	0.92	0.75
A1213	-22.94	0.33	26.52	-21.98	0.48	0.21	0.67	0.30	68.94
A1216	-21.10	0.25	136.23	-23.14	1.52	-2.42	0.33	0.43	3.07
A1238	-22.14	0.28	65.73	-21.72	0.50	-0.79	0.61	0.29	107.02
A1317	-22.41	0.27	66.73	-22.68	0.61	-1.46	0.38	0.21	44.28
A1318	-23.82	0.36	11.60	-24.15	0.92	-1.40	0.32	0.24	7.34
A1337	-23.26	0.39	11.32	-25.02	2.54	-1.98	0.45	0.91	0.72
A1344	-22.55	0.34	25.80	-23.47	1.32	-1.82	0.51	0.59	5.93
A1346	-22.73	0.32	48.22	-21.49	0.46	0.93	1.21	0.53	63.38
A1356	-23.32	0.29	28.01	-28.74	9.43	-2.14	0.14	0.54	0.01
A1365	-23.20	0.37	17.56	-22.21	0.64	-0.04	1.04	0.63	42.23
A1377	-23.07	0.31	26.43	-22.14	0.41	-0.43	0.45	0.17	74.63
A1383	-22.34	0.27	47.90	-22.49	0.54	-1.35	0.30	0.14	38.47
A1385	-22.61	0.43	11.06	-25.00	4.71	-2.27	0.65	2.45	0.18
A1399	-22.62	0.31	49.54	-21.56	0.48	0.43	1.06	0.49	85.17
A1412	-22.26	0.28	67.14	-21.38	0.39	-0.09	0.67	0.25	142.28
A1424	-22.40	0.28	56.44	-21.55	0.41	-0.22	0.62	0.24	125.87
A1436	-23.27	0.31	24.55	-22.12	0.36	-0.25	0.42	0.14	82.49
A1468	-23.00	0.35	22.25	-22.39	0.65	-0.65	0.73	0.44	44.92
A1474	-22.60	0.30	36.23	-22.34	0.57	-1.03	0.48	0.25	51.01
A1496	-23.11	0.36	22.87	-22.73	0.78	-0.86	0.84	0.61	36.81
A1526	-23.98	0.28	33.34	-24.12	0.54	-1.32	0.23	0.11	27.62
A1552	-23.24	0.30	34.63	-23.54	0.68	-1.43	0.33	0.20	22.49
A1609	-23.27	0.45	8.87	-26.01	6.50	-2.33	0.71	3.58	0.08
A1630	-22.49	0.42	14.21	-21.26	0.80	0.80	1.97	1.51	21.58
A1644	-22.82	0.27	34.57	-22.44	0.38	-1.04	0.21	0.08	56.30
A1650	-22.39	0.27	75.91	-22.33	0.53	-1.19	0.48	0.24	82.83

Table B.3: Fits to the Schechterfunction. Brightest cluster galaxies are excluded.

Abell	$M^*(2)$	σ_{M^*}	$n^*(2)$	$M^*(3)$	σ_{M^*}	α	σ_α	$cov(M^*, \alpha)$	$n^*(3)$
A1656	-22.45	0.18	163.14	-22.66	0.23	-1.35	0.08	0.02	122.68
A1668	-21.91	0.26	100.92	-21.80	0.49	-1.13	0.49	0.22	117.29
A1691	-22.88	0.32	28.63	-22.07	0.51	-0.40	0.66	0.31	67.79
A1749	-22.50	0.40	14.22	-21.97	0.92	-0.69	1.09	0.93	26.46
A1767	-22.38	0.29	46.52	-21.45	0.41	-0.15	0.63	0.24	110.53
A1773	-23.15	0.27	48.74	-25.61	1.69	-2.07	0.18	0.22	1.09
A1775	-22.91	0.28	37.78	-22.99	0.55	-1.30	0.30	0.14	33.82
A1780	-22.41	0.26	65.08	-21.59	0.33	-0.40	0.42	0.13	156.46
A1793	-22.14	0.39	30.00	-23.37	2.43	-2.25	1.09	2.41	3.19
A1795	-22.41	0.27	54.83	-22.69	0.59	-1.44	0.33	0.17	36.35
A1809	-22.68	0.27	63.94	-24.06	1.02	-1.97	0.27	0.23	6.76
A1827	-23.23	0.38	12.60	-22.42	0.69	-0.49	0.78	0.49	31.29
A1831	-21.99	0.25	95.61	-22.86	0.74	-1.84	0.32	0.21	23.39
A1892	-22.41	0.36	31.35	-22.35	1.01	-1.19	1.07	1.01	33.74
A1904	-23.00	0.28	40.55	-23.38	0.62	-1.47	0.27	0.14	23.23
A1913	-23.00	0.28	32.92	-22.96	0.48	-1.23	0.23	0.09	34.83
A1927	-22.86	0.36	17.02	-23.74	1.40	-1.74	0.49	0.59	4.33
A1939	-22.64	0.37	25.06	-25.34	4.72	-2.48	0.60	2.27	0.18
A1983	-22.39	0.28	48.77	-21.43	0.34	-0.26	0.46	0.15	128.80
A1991	-22.44	0.32	41.09	-21.79	0.57	-0.47	0.83	0.45	79.54
A2018	-22.30	0.27	69.19	-22.32	0.57	-1.26	0.48	0.25	67.88
A2022	-22.98	0.31	26.61	-22.84	0.61	-1.16	0.39	0.21	31.95
A2028	-23.43	0.32	25.18	-23.13	0.62	-1.02	0.48	0.27	37.19
A2029	-22.36	0.23	129.32	-21.55	0.26	-0.31	0.38	0.09	291.43
A2040	-22.59	0.31	36.03	-22.06	0.57	-0.70	0.66	0.35	67.17
A2048	-23.40	0.30	31.89	-22.77	0.47	-0.69	0.46	0.20	68.26
A2056	-22.51	0.33	32.83	-22.30	0.71	-1.06	0.66	0.43	43.10
A2061	-23.28	0.26	46.08	-22.50	0.32	-0.65	0.29	0.08	115.43
A2067	-22.41	0.30	45.86	-22.72	0.76	-1.49	0.47	0.32	28.82
A2079	-22.76	0.25	68.37	-22.98	0.49	-1.40	0.26	0.11	49.46
A2089	-22.62	0.31	30.80	-22.92	0.77	-1.45	0.41	0.28	19.99
A2092	-22.48	0.34	25.41	-21.44	0.51	-0.02	0.81	0.38	63.56
A2107	-21.63	0.25	69.72	-21.46	0.38	-1.13	0.26	0.09	87.83

Table B.3: Fits to the Schechterfunction. Brightest cluster galaxies are excluded.

Abell	$M^*(2)$	σ_{M^*}	$n^*(2)$	$M^*(3)$	σ_{M^*}	α	σ_α	$cov(M^*, \alpha)$	$n^*(3)$
A2110	-22.53	0.36	30.61	-21.15	0.56	1.38	1.67	0.89	28.47
A2122	-22.38	0.28	55.67	-22.07	0.50	-0.95	0.48	0.22	83.37
A2142	-22.69	0.27	55.28	-22.09	0.37	-0.71	0.37	0.13	113.87
A2147	-22.28	0.24	71.17	-21.71	0.28	-0.84	0.22	0.05	144.34
A2151	-22.97	0.25	38.22	-22.38	0.29	-0.95	0.15	0.04	79.80
A2152	-21.57	0.20	122.80	-22.59	0.43	-1.67	0.10	0.04	28.06
A2175	-22.86	0.27	63.52	-22.29	0.40	-0.69	0.45	0.16	123.38
A2197	-22.72	0.25	34.51	-23.02	0.43	-1.36	0.11	0.04	23.35
A2198	-21.72	0.30	63.80	-21.91	0.79	-1.44	0.69	0.51	48.18
A2199	-22.60	0.25	37.53	-21.72	0.25	-0.77	0.15	0.03	108.18
A2244	-22.89	0.23	133.56	-22.67	0.37	-1.03	0.37	0.13	177.68
A2245	-22.20	0.27	79.13	-22.54	0.65	-1.53	0.44	0.26	47.70
A2250	-22.28	0.23	103.88	-23.50	0.65	-1.85	0.17	0.09	15.43
A2255	-22.84	0.22	100.82	-22.39	0.27	-0.90	0.22	0.05	178.70
A2256	-23.10	0.26	45.53	-21.91	0.26	-0.22	0.30	0.07	158.38
mean	-22.65	0.30	49.26	-22.70	0.95	-1.022	0.52	0.43	61.6
	± 0.48			± 1.24		± 0.77			
median	-22.60			-22.41		-1.05			
	± 0.48			± 1.28		± 0.78			

Appendix C

Figures

This appendix contains page filling figures. The figures belong to chapter 3 and chapter 4. For additional information see those chapters.

Figure C.1: Cluster LFs plus best fitting Schechter function (brightest cluster members are included).

Figure C.2: Cluster LFs plus best fitting Schechter function (brightest cluster members are included).

Figure C.3: Cluster LFs plus best fitting Schechter function (brightest cluster members are included). The x points give the counts uncorrected for non-cluster members, the squares show the corrected counts.

Figure C.4: Cluster LFs plus best fitting Schechter function (brightest cluster members are included). The x points give the counts uncorrected for non-cluster members, the squares show the corrected counts.

Figure C.5: Cluster LFs plus best fitting Schechter function (brightest cluster members are included). The x points give the counts uncorrected for non-cluster members, the squares show the corrected counts.

Figure C.6: Cluster LFs plus best fitting Schechter function (brightest cluster members are included). The x points give the counts uncorrected for non-cluster members, the squares show the corrected counts.

Figure C.7: Cluster LFs plus best fitting Schechter function (brightest cluster members are included). The x points give the counts uncorrected for non-cluster members, the squares show the corrected counts.

Figure C.8: Cluster LFs plus best fitting Schechter function (brightest cluster members are included). The x points give the counts uncorrected for non-cluster members, the squares show the corrected counts.

Figure C.9: Cluster LFs plus best fitting Schechter function (brightest cluster members are included). The x points give the counts uncorrected for non-cluster members, the squares show the corrected counts.

Figure C.10: Standard deviations and correlations of the Monte Carlo runs, for different numbers of galaxies and for different M_{im} .

Figure C.11: Fitted parameters of Monte Carlo generated LFs. All these LFs had a limiting magnitude $M_{lim} = -19.0$. The number gives the number of "galaxies" per LF.

Figure C.12: Fitted parameters of Monte Carlo generated LFs. All these LFs had a limiting magnitude $M_{lim} = -21.0$. The number gives the number of “galaxies” per LF.

Figure C.13: Composite LFs for different subsamples based on richness. Shown are the LFs made including brightest cluster members (left) and excluding them (see text).

Figure C.14: Fitted parameters to composite LFs of randomly chosen subsamples from the total, the poor cluster, medium rich and rich clusters samples. On average 50% of the clusters from the original sample participated in these fits.

Figure C.15: Composite LFs of samples with different velocity dispersion and the samples made on basis of Bautz-Morgan (BM) type.

Figure C.17: Inside and outside LFs for the $BM \leq II$ and $BM > II$ samples.

Figure C.16: The LF of the inner region (i.e. galaxies within $0.5 Mpc$ from the cluster center) and the outer region of cluster. The samples are based on different richness class (RN).

Figure C.18: Inside and outside LFs for the $\sigma_v < 800 \text{ km/s}$ and $\sigma_v > 800 \text{ km/s}$ samples.

Figure C.19: Inside LFs excluding the brightest cluster member for various samples.

Figure C.20: The difference between the inside and outside *integrated* distributions is shown. A positive value indicates an excess of galaxies in the center of the cluster. Inside and outside are chosen such that both areas have the same size. Here the outside region is a ring with outside radius $1.5Mpc$ and inside radius $1.1Mpc$.

Figure C.21: This figure is the same as the previous figure, only a more central region is shown. Here the inside region is a circular area with a radius $0.7 Mpc$, whereas the outside ring has an outer radius $1.0 Mpc$.